

IPv6 Routing protocol for low power and lossy networks (RPL) with Load balancing (Burst Traffic Scenarios)

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Abstract

The volume of research performed in the domain of Wireless Sensor Networks has increased substantially in recent years. This is due to the advancement of fabrication technology of low-power devices containing various sensors along with a wireless interface, allowing costs to be reduced. Therefore, the deployment of large-scale sensor networks, which could consist of several thousand nodes, still represents a challenge as it is produced in a large amount of heterogeneous data that are shaped at an exponential rate. This thesis aims to evaluate the performance of routing protocols in lossy links for smart building networks. Special attention is directed towards the IPv6 Routing Protocol for Low Power and Lossy Network (RPL) which is the IETF candidate for a standard routing protocol in wireless sensor networks. The performance of RPL suffers in a network with burst traffic load, which leads to reducing the lifetime of the network and causing traffic congestion among the neighbour nodes. In Low Power and Lossy Networks (LLNs) sensor nodes are deployed in various traffic load conditions such as regular and heavy traffic load. In large events, burst traffic load requires a new radical approach of load balancing, this scenario causes congestion increases and packet drops relatively when frequent traffic burst load rises in comparison with regular and heavy loads. Therefore, based on aforementioned issues proposed research firstly provides the traffic-aware metric that utilizes ETX and parent count metrics (ETXPC), where communication quality for LLNs with RPL routing protocol are playing an important role in traffic engineering. In addition, this research will provide analytical results to quantify the impact of Minimum Rank with Hysteresis Objective on Function (MRHOF) and Objective Function Zero (OF0) to the packet delivery, reliability and power consumption in LLNs. Secondly, in the proposed work a Burst and Congestion-Aware Metric for RPL called BCA-RPL, which calculates the rank, considering the number of packets. Also, the proposed mechanism includes congestion avoiding and load balancing techniques by switching the best parent selection to avoid the congested area. Simulation results based on the Cooja simulator shows BCA-RPL performs better than the original RPL-OF0 routing protocol in terms of packet

loss, power consumption and packet delivery ratio (PDR) under burst traffic load. Thirdly, the main contribution introduces a mechanism called BT-RPL to address the problem of packet loss and burst traffic power used in RPL to address this problem in two steps. First, this work avoid congestion and load balancing issues with the help of rank calculation with attention to the number of packets. The parent selection mechanism is constructed and compared with the default RPL routing protocol with OF0. Secondly, also evaluated the results on the Cooja simulator, which indicates that the proposed technique to avoid congestion and a load balancing problem outperformed the default RPL routing protocol with OF0. Based on the proposed test-bed evaluation, the BT-RPL has reduced packet loss by around 80% and energy consumption, which is an acceptable level of the IoT network design. In addition to this, average latency accuracy performance is also maintained. This study also comprehensively analysed and compared the overall results in terms of different packet reception ration RX.

Abbreviation	Full Form
WSN	Wireless Sensor Network
LLN	Low power and Lossy Network
MANET	Mobile Ad hoc Network Force
IETF	Internet Engineering Task
ROLL	Routing Over Low power and Lossy networks
RPL	Routing Protocol for Low power and Lossy networks
DSDV	Destination-Sequenced Distance Vector
AODV	Ad hoc On-Demand Distance Vector
DSR	Dynamic Source Routing
RIP	Routing Information Protocol
OSPF	Open Shortest Path First
EIGRP	Enhanced Interior Gateway Routing Protocol
IS-IS	Intermediate System to Intermediate System
MAC	Medium Access Control
DODAG	Destination Oriented Directed Acyclic Graph
DIO	DODAG Information Object
DAO	Destination Advertisement Object
CPU	Central Processing Unit
MCU	Microcontroller Unit
ACK	Acknowledgement
NAK	Negative Acknowledgement

Declaration of Authorship

I, Hussien Altwassi, hereby declare that my thesis with the title of “IPv6 Routing Protocol for low power and lossy networks (RPL) with Load balancing (Burst Traffic Scenarios).” is entirely my original work. This study has not utilised any authors sources other than those are mentioned in the bibliography. In addition to this, this research work has not submitted to any other institution for any purpose. I am aware of the University of West of Scotland regulations and plagiarism concerns. 1. The whole work is carried out as a major part of achieving a PhD research degree from this university. 2. Wherever I have mentioned the other authors published work has been attributed. 3. Wherever I have provided the quotations from the existing researchers, an accurate source is also provided with a bibliography. 4. My proposed research is also acknowledged with all significant sources.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Internet of things (IoT) consists of a large number of wireless sensor devices which are low energy and wirelessly interconnected to enable them to communicate through a radio interface. Today, IoT applications are deployed underwater, on the ground and underground [1]. Low-power Communications and processor units are looking to investigate the functionalities of the embedded system with less energy of data routing, the main aim of the communication between sensor nodes is data routing and sharing. Each sensor typically acts as a data forwarder and a data originator at the same time [2]. Also, a huge amount of data is often generated via deployed sensors in IoT applications that generate a huge volume of data [3]. Opportunities presented by the IoT offer the potential for a vast quantity of applications to be in our world, while, only a very small quantity is available to our environment at this time, Also, most of these applications are separated into numerous domains such as, ‘Smart Environment (office, home, plant), ‘Healthcare’, ‘Transportation’ and ‘Personal and Social’ [4]. Currently, there has been major growth in applications that are under critical conditions such as burst traffic, where these applications did not request to send continuous data, These applications are operated within a technique of changing periods of data transmission where there is little data to be sent or no data is sent. Also, it generates bursts of data separated by application-limited periods. For example, applications that result in such traffic include sports events, online games and video conferencing, etc [5]. In detail, burst traffic is one of the IoT application scenarios, where massive data is generated in specific time slots. In certain burst traffic scenarios, the receiving nodes will record a high packet drop probability due to the buffer size limitation problems and congestions. For example, it is common to have a node with relatively higher traffic than neighbouring nodes in RPL, due to the missing load balance feature in RPL. In this case, the parent

node can be severely congested and drop many packets due to these limitations. Generally, the burst delivery happens when myriad nodes start sending messages in response to a specific event in a relatively smaller duration of time.

Routing is a critical function in the Internet of Things, with multiple protocols that rely on the availability of an underlying service and several applications. The routing protocol considers the routing path to determine the best routes routing protocols using a suitable algorithm – where the routing path has a substantial impact on a protocol’s effectiveness. Routing channels for data packet transfer from one node to another can be set up in one of three ways: proactively, responsive, or mixed. [14]. Routing over Lossy and Low-Power Networks (ROLL) The Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) convened a working group to create the RPL routing protocol, which addresses routing in low-power lossy networks in a standard fashion. As a result, in the IoT environment, to handle the varied application requirements of the networks [7]. The objective function (OF) is the basis of the RPL procedures to achieve improved routing performance in various types of networks using relevant metrics, where one or more metrics can be mixed while picking a route, according to the RPL standard’s architecture. Although RPL is flexible to accommodate any optimization techniques, it is feasible to get pretty incredible performance in any given case [8]. This work investigated the most recent RPL-related studies, which may be roughly divided into two categories: (1) RPL performance assessment, (2) RPL modelling and integration Despite the fact that there have been several performance assessment studies on RPL in LLNs, there is still a gap in RPL’s performance technique in the IoT context that has to be filled, particularly for networks experiencing burst traffic. The major goal of our method will be to focus on BCA-RPL, a Burst and Congestion-Aware Metric for RPL that determines the rank based on the amount of packets. Congestion avoidance and load balancing approaches are also included in the suggested process, which involves switching the optimal parent selection to avoid the crowded location. Furthermore, using burst traffic over burst multi-hop LLN situations, this study will propose BT-RPL to combine load balancing with RPL in 6LoWPAN. Furthermore, in order to conserve energy by calibrating the RPL settings, this field must be thoroughly investigated. As a result, we will investigate our goals using simulator simulations using the RPL’s most significant factors, including as node density, packet reception ratio, and topologies. These parameters can have an impact on RPL design, hence it’s worth looking into and evaluating the impact of this parameter on RPL performance; will help to determine our gap. In addition to this may need other parameters evaluation such as throughput and latency to support our work. To fill the gap, this study first reviews the existing efforts on IoT and then presents an extensive literature review of RPL) In particular, this chapter conducts a comprehensive overview of

IoT concerning IoT Routing protocol, low power and lossy networks (LLNs) and present the foundation of monitoring application -based of the IoT.

1.2 Motivations

The development of the IoT and its applications has engaged the attention of numerous researchers. To provide IPv6 support for the IoT devices, the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) anticipated the 6LoWPAN stack, see figure 1-1. However, the hardware restrictions of networks connected with IoT devices cause several challenges, mostly for routing protocols. On its stack proposal, IETF standardizes the RPL (IPv6 Routing Protocol for Low-Power and Lossy Networks) as the routing protocol for Low-power and Lossy Networks (LLNs). As shown in 1.1, RPL is a proactive routing algorithm based on trees that produces acyclic networks between nodes to facilitate data sharing [7].

Figure 1.1: IoT Subsystem using RP

Based on the number of existing literature devoted to the development of RPL focused on its objective function, my thesis offers a chance to address a range of replicated solutions and brings further encouragement to the creation of new decision variables according to the burst traffic scenarios of the LLNs application. In contrast, the current thesis makes it so much easier to eliminate common variations

of routing metrics and to provide a clear insight into discrepancies in metrics and limitations. This study is the first to concentrate on the main Routing variable, namely the Analytical Function, relative to the current RPL assessments. Thus, it offers a detailed description of the routing criteria used only for rank computing. In particular, this study discusses the various methods reported yet for routing metric configurations. This then suggests the in-depth analysis, based on data, of the research hard work made to determine the OF, to extrapolate the advantages and deficiencies of the criteria of the OFs. Related to other RPL studies, the present study addresses the technological changes which make it easier to transcend the shortcomings of the objective function-focused mostly on composite or single metrics.

1.3 Challenges

Burst traffic is one of the IoT application scenarios, where massive data is generated in specific time slots. In certain burst traffic scenarios, the receiving nodes will record a high packet drop probability due to the buffer size limitation problems and congestions. For example, it is common to have a node with relatively higher traffic than neighbouring nodes in RPL, due to the missing load balance feature in RPL. In this case, the parent node can be severely congested and drop many packets due to these limitations. Generally, the burst delivery happens when myriad nodes start sending messages in response to a specific event in a relatively smaller duration of time. For instance, in a network using RPL with MHROF based on ETX metric, nodes will choose the parents with the best link quality. Considering a network with non-uniform distribution and uneven data traffic may result in a significant load imbalance. The sensor nodes that have links of better quality will forward more packets than others. Thereby, their energy depletion will be notably faster than the nodes with light traffic, and thus, gaps and holes in the network will appear, reducing the network lifetime. Followed by IoT literature, the RPL and its OF were primarily targeting only for low power and lossy network, it is found a serious load balancing problem in a network once heavy traffic load applied within RPL. Therefore, more complicated load balancing issues will create alarming situations during the event of a burst traffic load. As load-balancing become an issue in the RPL, some efforts have been discussed for the load balancing problem using multiple gateways to spread the load of the traffic to more than one sink

1.4 Research Objective

The main goal of my study is to explore the use of RPL objective functions under regular and burst traffic conditions, also to provide concepts from RPL routing protocol along with the optimization techniques to solve the critical load balancing problem in RPL which is become a hot research area in Internet-of-Things (IoT). In summary, our aim is to propose enhancement/optimization in objective functions of RPL. However, results will be shown using extensive simulation experiments on the Cooja simulator as one of the IoT tools, which can provide many advantages over IoT. To achieve this, the progress will be built by:

1. Present an extensive literature review of the IPv6 Routing Protocol for Low Power and Lossy Network (RPL).
2. Identify potential strengths and weaknesses of IoT routing techniques.
3. To propos a traffic-aware metric that utilizes ETX and parent count metrics (ETXPC), by Employing extensive simulation experiments as a starting point with the optimization techniques to solve the critical load balancing problem in RPL routing protocol for burst traffic conditions.
4. Introduced a new efficient load balance mechanism for traffic congestion called BCA-RPL in IPv6 Routing Protocol for Low Power and Lossy Network (RPL) to measure the communication quality and optimize the lifetime of the network.
5. Identify existing gaps and areas of improvements/integration of available tools with research already in progress that is related to the proposed problem.
6. Present the OF RPL load balancing scheme called Burst Traffic BT- RPL to address the problem of RPL load balancing in RPL based on packet delivery ratio (PDR), power consumption (PC) and latency.

1.5 Contributions

Firstly, the major aim of the research will be focused on proposing a traffic-aware metric that utilizes ETX and parent count metrics (ETXPC), where communication quality for LLNs with RPL routing protocol are playing an important role in traffic engineering. In addition, also provide analytical results to quantify the impact of Minimum Rank with Hysteresis Objective on Function (MRHOF) and Objective Function Zero (OF0) to the packet delivery, reliability and power consumption in LLNs. The simulation results pragmatically show that the proposed load balancing approach has increased the packet delivery ratio with less power consumption. Secondly, this study will focus on proposing a Burst and Congestion-Aware Metric for RPL called BCA-RPL, which calculates the rank, considering the number of packets. Also, the proposed mechanism includes congestion avoiding and load

balancing techniques by switching the best parent selection to avoid the congested area. Our scheme is built and compared to the original RPL routing protocol for low power and loss networks with OF0 (OF0-RPL). Simulation results based on the Cooja simulator shows BCA-RPL performs better than the original RPL-OF0 routing protocol in terms of packet loss, power consumption and packet delivery ratio (PDR) under burst traffic load. The BCA-RPL significantly improves the network where it is decreased the packet loss by around 50% and power consumption to an acceptable level with an improvement on the PDR of the IoT network. Thirdly, In this study, a mechanism called BT-RPL address the problem of packet loss and burst traffic power used in RPL. First of all, will address this problem in two steps, then to avoid congestion and load balancing issues with the help of rank calculation with attention to the number of packets. The parent selection mechanism is constructed and compared with the default RPL routing protocol with OF0. Secondly, this research will evaluate the results on the Cooja simulator, which indicates that the proposed technique to avoid congestion and a load balancing problem outperformed the default RPL routing protocol with OF0. Based on the proposed test-bed evaluation, the BT-RPL has reduced packet loss by around 80% and energy consumption, which is an acceptable level of the IoT network design. In addition to this, average latency accuracy performance is also maintained. Also comprehensively analyzed and compared the overall results in terms of different packet reception ration RX.

1.6 Thesis Outline

The structure of this thesis is started with an introductory chapter to provide a full vision of the work. This work begins in Chapter 2 with a description of the internet of things networks, their characteristics and limitations before tackling the emerging trend towards RPL routing protocol with burst traffic scenarios in particular. The IPv6 low power and lossy networks (RPL) standard along with the resulting standardisation efforts, relevant to this thesis, are then presented. This chapter ends by discussing the related work used in this research project. Chapter 3 introduce a new efficient load balance mechanism for traffic congestion in IPv6 Routing Protocol for Low Power and Lossy Network (RPL). To measure the communication quality and optimize the lifetime of the network, in this research have chosen packet delivery ratio (PDR) and power consumption (PC) as our metrics. This study also proposed a traffic-aware metric that utilizes ETX and parent count metrics (ETXPC), where communication quality for LLNs with RPL routing protocol are playing an important role in traffic engineering. Chapter 4 propose a Burst and Congestion-Aware Metric for RPL called BCA-RPL, which calculates the rank, considering the number of packets. Also, the proposed mechanism includes congestion avoiding and load

balancing techniques by switching the best parent selection to avoid the congested area. Chapter 5 introduce a mechanism called BT-RPL to address the problem of packet loss and burst traffic power used in RPL, and addressed this problem in two steps. First, the author has avoided congestion and load balancing issues with the help of rank calculation with attention to the number of packets. The parent selection mechanism is constructed and compared with the default RPL routing protocol with OF0. Chapter 6, concentrate on the core RPL variable, such as the OF. Also, it offers a detailed description of the routing parameters used during rank computing. Our research discusses the various methods that have been reported to date for routing metric variations. This then suggests a very deep analysis, based on data, of the research hard work made to determine the objective function, intending to extrapolate the advantages and deficiencies of the criteria of the OFs. Finally, chapter 7 achieve our objective summary by stressing the diverse challenges and matters which can be set for future works as well as critical future works based on our vision.

1.7 Publications

1. **Hussien Saleh Altwassi**, Zeeshan Pervez, Keshav Dahal and Baraq Ghaleb. “The RPL Load Balancing in IoT Network with Burst Traffic Scenarios” 12th International Conference on Software, Knowledge, Information Management Applications 3-5 Dec 2018, Phnom Penh, Cambodia
2. **1. Hussien Saleh Altwassi**, Pervez, Z. and Dahal, K., 2019, August. A Burst and Congestion-Aware Routing Metric for RPL Protocol in IoT Network. In 2019 13th International Conference on Software, Knowledge, Information Management and Applications (SKIMA) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.

Chapter 2

Background and Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

Routing over Low power and Lossy networks (ROLL) Working Group assembled and called by the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) To develop the RPL routing protocol to address routing in low-power lossy networks in a standard way. RPL has been developed keeping in mind the constraints posed by the 6LoWPAN adaptation layer, thereby making it a good choice for routing in embedded IPv6 networks. Therefore, to manage the various application necessities of the networks in the IoT environment [7]. Based on the design of the RPL standard, the objective function (OF) is the core of the RPL mechanisms to develop the performance of routing in various types of networks using suitable metrics, where one or more metrics can be combined while choosing a route[16].

This work proposes a new load balancing mechanism for the RPL protocol that has multi-hop data collection applications, such as environmental monitoring in the critical event (sport, disaster, festivals). Our scheme is starting with a traffic manager to update the traffic route analyzing the traffic and discover the delivery mode which could be regular or burst, then it will employ threshold of the ETX value and parent count (the number of candidate parents) to compute and detect the most efficient path to the sink. Our traffic management offers functionality to avoid congestions.

2.2 Overview of Internet of Things (IoT)

Internet of Things (IoT) is a driving technology to revolutionize the current Internet by expanding it with a large number of smart objects (WSN nodes, embedded

Figure 2.1: Simplified RPL Features Classes Diagrams Integrated with Objective Container

systems, smartphones, etc.) [9]. However, Opportunities presented by the IoT offer the potential for a vast quantity of applications to be in our world, while, only a very small quantity is available to our environment at this time, also, most of these applications are separated into numerous domains such as, Smart Environment (office, home, plant), Healthcare, and Social [4]. Sensors can use various forms of wide-area networking, like Global Mobile Communications System (GSM), Third Generation (3 G), Long-Term Evolution (LTE) and General Packet Radio Service (GPRS). Also, Sensors can provide local area interactions, including such relatively close-field connectivity (NFC), wireless fidelity (Wi-Fi) and radiofrequency recognition (RFID). [9] [10]. However, In [11][12][13] presented the enabling technologies, protocols, and possible applications of IoT, in which the horizontal overview of IoT was provided and the key IoT challenges including Unreliability of links and network dynamicity, autoconfiguration and parameters constrained routing have presented to point out the future directions [18].

2.3 IoT Routing

Routing in IoT is the main technique between sensor nodes to route and share the data. Each node from a sensor typically acts as a data forwarder and a data originator at the same time to the destination via links (single or multi-hop). The number of these nodes is different depending on the network, where three types of the network are classified as light, medium and large-scale networks regarding its density network. [2] In proactive routing, all the routes are computed by gathering the routing information proactively which mean by advance; and then maintaining a balance to update the routing information from each node to all other nodes in the network. This is full monitoring of the changes into the topology to make sure that the availability of any route between active nodes is ready. Also, Proactive Routing Protocols are called table-driven protocols, For example, once topology progress gets changed as a result of the failure of nodes, these routing information changes have to be propagated via the network as updates. This propagated on the Routing updates is the reason behind the variation of the number of routing approaches and tables maintained in routing protocols [14]. The main characteristics of these protocols include:

- Shortest-path protocols
- Distributed
- High routing overhead and consumes more bandwidth
- Based on Periodic updates of the routing table
- Maintain routes between every host pair at all times

In reactive, source or destination can start to discover the routes when it is required. Also, Reactive Routing Protocols are called demand-driven. Typically, it means that once the source started, the source node will initiate the discovery process, while once the destination started, the destination node will initiate the discovery process. Moreover, this type of routing does not support the nodes to begin a route discovery process until a route to a destination is desired. However, a significant amount of energy will expand in route discovery and setup until it is finished. For the route still processor is required again, a maintenance procedure is ready by preserving route discovery [14]. The main characteristics of these routing protocols are:

- Less routing overhead.
- Determine routes as and when required

- More route discovery delay
- Source initiated route discovery

Hybrid routing is the idea behind both reactive and proactive characteristics, which is combined to make routing protocols more efficient and scalable [14]. In addition, different approaches to routing protocols have been combined to form a single protocol. For example, Zone Routing Protocol (ZRP) is one such protocol that combines the reactive and proactive approaches. Main characteristics include: Combination of selected features of proactive and reactive protocols, Adaptive to network condition.

2.3.1 IEEE

As Standardization efforts relevant to IoT are mainly into two Organizations: (1) the IEEE and (2) the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF). IEEE generally standardizes: The physical layer, Medium access protocols. The IEEE 802.15.4 proposes an extensive global standard accepted at MAC and PHY level by IoT network for interconnecting both the low-power/data-rate/cost IoT nodes and the actuator networks. Also, The IEEE 802.15.4 is standard for ubiquitous networks that response to a varied range of application cases, for example, home automation, building surveillance and health monitoring [4]. The Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) includes a vast number of active WGs organized in diverse research areas. The IETF WGs related to IoT are : 1. IETF 6LoWPAN (Dedicated to providing end-to-end IPv6 connectivity in IoT networks), 2. IETF ROLL (Routing over Low power and Lossy links). 6LoWPAN was designed from the beginning to be adapted in the future with IPv6- to support sensor networks. It is a developing standard of the (IETF) 6LoWPAN Working Group [6]. Recently, their progress was focused on the steps to provide more efficiency and saleability Low-power and Lossy networks (LLNs) scenario by optimizing the network routing and self-organization progression. RPL (IPv6 Routing Protocol for LLNs) is one of its standard protocols proposed by this working group, it was built over a traditional distance vector routing paradigm [6]. ROLL group has worked for providing RPL protocol with efficiently support including three network traffic patterns: Firstly, Point to Point (P2P) is a network traffic pattern that uses a technique each minute for every sensor in the LLN by unicasting around (200 bytes) of sensor data to its associated controller. Unfortunately, each sensor expects an application acknowledgement unicast returned from the destination. Also, each controller will unicast messages at an insignificant rate of 6 kbit/minute to supervisory or peer controllers. 30% of each node's packets are guided towards other nodes within the LLN. Secondly, MultiPoint

to Point (MP2P) is a network traffic pattern that controls the rest of each node's packets which are 70% guided towards an aggregation device, then it will be routed off the LLN. In MP2P messages, a unicast acknowledgement from the destination is also required. In addition, the values on Point to point (P2P) section are assumed a straight node-to-node communication; error and meshing retransmissions are not considered. Finally, point to multipoint (P2MP) is a Multicasting traffic pattern that occurred to all nodes in LLN once the root node sends the messages towards other nodes as object discovery during first commissioned in the network. Lighting systems will also readily use multicasting during normal operations to turn banks of lights "on" and "off" simultaneously. For example, multicasting is used in lighting systems during normal operations to turn banks of lights "off" and "on".

2.3.2 ROLL

Routing Over Low power and Lossy networks (ROLL) Working Group is driving the work with IPv6 routing protocol for Low power and Lossy Networks (RPL) via Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) RFC such as [16] [17] [18]. The IETF ROLL Group has implemented this protocol to deliver opportunities that can attain employment for IoT over WSN [14]. The separation of OFs from the core protocol specification allows RPL to be adapted to meet the different optimization routes required by the wide range of deployments, applications, and network designs [15]. Which mean optimisation will focus on the LLN requirements. For example, optimizing the RPL link quality is relying on the deployments, applications, and network designs that have an impact on the RPL link quality.

2.4 IoT applications Deployments

IoT allows information gathering, transmitting and storing be available and presented for things equipped with the sensors. The various number of sensors have been widely used in environmental monitoring, manufacturing, supply chain management, retailing, travel and tourism industry, healthcare, food and restaurant industry, smart shelf operations and logistic industry [13]. Currently, IoT has already been deployed in several areas successfully: Into manufacturers, the number of products is increasing which is made with a special identification technology. These types of technologies let the products be under tracked and monitored in their life cycles such instance RFID tags, barcodes and home appliances. In addition, these technologies introduce new processing techniques and data exchange which plays an important role to increase the effectiveness of traditional industries. Into users, a massive number of software and hardware components (mobile applications, mobile

phones, social networks and RFID tags) have been established for the customers that allow users to have access to extra information regarding products. On the other hand, The ROLL Working Group has introduced documents detailing the routing requirements about four deployments scenarios - Urban LLN deployments in RFC 5548 [17], Industrial Automation LLN deployments in RFC 5673 [16], Home LLN deployments in RFC 5826 (5), and Building LLN deployments in RFC 5867 (18). There are various challenges regarding routing in these deployments including Unreliability of links and network dynamicity, Autoconfiguration and Parameter constrained routing. Also, the device capacity and link characteristics cause more inquiries for proper operation routing protocol within the LLNs. Moreover, the devices would face significant challenges due to their inability to store detailed network routing states. The LLN devices are typically powered by batteries. At the same time, different deployment scenarios have various requirements based on their traffic characteristics, application profile and criticality of application data. Therefore, last, a few years was expected that without any power source there is no opportunity for energy scavenging.

2.5 Low Power and Lossy Networks (LLNs)

Low power and lossy networks (LLNs) are a type of network that purpose to make both the routers as well as its interconnection. Also, LLN routers are regularly functioning with constraints on memory, processing power and energy (battery power). [19] There are many characteristics of LLNs case a differentiation from the standard networks significantly with a highly resource-constrained at both routers and interconnects: 1. Routers are constrained in terms of memory, processing power and battery life. 2. The interconnects are lossy with a high packet drop rate. Also, these types of networks could comprise hundreds or thousands of nodes. Moreover, they have to support multiple types of traffic patterns (such as MP2P and P2P) as well as use a wide variety of communication technologies including both wired and wireless. Since IoT networks are commonly deployed in environments with high data-traffic stream [46], it is essential to concerns in our account as a hot gap need to be addressed while designing a routing protocol for LLNs. Therefore, a high data-traffic stream needs to be addressed to see the impact that causes saleability in the network performance in terms of packet loss, delay and congestion [20]. Many routing protocols have been evaluated by the ROLL working group to find out if they are satisfied with the requirements of LLNs or not, for example: 1. Intermediate System to Intermediate System (IS-IS) [21]. 2. Open Shortest Path First (OSPF) [22]. 3. Optimized Link State Routing (OLSR) [23]. 4. Ad Hoc on Demand Vector (AODV) [24]. But sadly, they are not successfully protocoled to satisfy with characteristics

Figure 2.2: Architecture of RPL Routing Support for Stadium and Sport Event Automation Control System

of the links and nodes in the LLNs network. For example, path selection has to be designed to concern the specific, functional, attributes and power capabilities. [25]. Therefore, Routing solutions for these cases should consider different traffic patterns based on the application nature, such as many-to-many, many-to-one, and one-to-many. This requirement has pushed most of the IoT scenarios to tackle their obstacles with one of the two active routing algorithms: AODV and RPL. Mostly because these two routing protocols provide very good performance in these scenarios as well as present low complexity.

2.5.1 Ad Hoc on Demand Vector (AODV)

AODV is one of the most popular used protocols regarding its benefits. For example, self-repair, small computation and reactive routing protocol. However, AODV is focusing on the Number of hops to select a route. Moreover, this protocol often fits less reliable routes guiding towards packet loss and high control overhead. On other

Figure 2.3: Architecture of Stadium and Sport Event Automation Control System

hand, Though AODV protocol is a broadly used reactive type routing protocol in a Mobile Ad Hoc Network (MANET) which can do well in terms of delivery ratio throughput and delay, it still has poor overhead and scalability issues [26]. AODV [24] is using Route Request (RREQ) and Route Reply (RREP) messages to discover the route in between nodes. The main issue in this protocol. The features of this mechanism once employed on the network could not give the guarantee that will provide an efficiency of the convergence time, control overhead and energy. Also, this mechanism with low-/medium-densities will have a lake which causes a drain of resources for constrained scenarios. It is resources could be a drain if there is any problem with the route in case if a new route is desired to be discovered because AODV did not use another route, which means it does not use more than one route for the destination node.

2.5.2 IPv6 Routing Protocol for Low Power and Lossy Networks (RPL)

In this section, the main focus will be related to the RPL protocol which IPv6 Routing Protocol is designed for Low Power and Lossy Networks (LLN). However, the RPL is a distance vector routing protocol which is a suitable scheme for the IoT based LLN, the essential aspect of RPL is the Objective Function (OF), which defines the method that is usually used to calculate the nodes rank by utilizing one or more metric and constraint [30]. Low power and lossy networks (LLNs) are a type of network that purpose to make both the routers as well as its interconnection. Also, LLN routers are regularly functioning with constraints on memory, processing power and energy (battery power) [19]. An overview of the RPL process in detail will be in the next chapter [7].

Figure 2.4: RPL Structure Data Collection

In Figure 2.4, the RPL routing protocol is building a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) to reform the physical topology. Each graph includes one or more instances. To provide greater scalability, the whole topology within these instances is divided into various Destination Oriented DAGs (DODAGs) [7]. The programme of the message's movement within the DODAG is in two ways: Either, From the top to the bottom.2. Either, From the bottom (leaves) to the top (root). These two paths are called routing downward and routing upward respectively.

2.6 Comparison of IoT Routing Protocols

Although, the number of Internet users has been increased as well as the speed of the fastest links, still the Internet protocols core has not changed significantly from a long period [27]. An extensive series of solutions have been proposed in the literature to tackle the issue of increasing Internet's users number, each of these solutions is aiming to solve or support Parameter constrained routing, auto-configuration, Unreliability of links, network dynamicity, load balancing and other requirements that can be considered for developing new routing protocols. [27]. Well-known routing protocols proposed for LLNs and related to standard protocols are introduced in this Section. Also, a characteristics comparison with RPL can be a notice from the as well as an overview on these routing protocols. AODV has been considered a suitable algorithm for LLNs as mentioned in the previous section [24]. But still, some changes are essentially required to modify AODV to suit strongly with 6LoWPAN environments. LOAD [25] enhances the AODV protocol according to 6LoWPAN requirements. AODV enhancements in detail are summarised as below: LOAD is a routing protocol belonging to the AODV standard while LOAD reduces the implementation complexity. Also, LOAD offers load balancing support in the network as compared to AODV. LOAD focuses during the route discovery phase only with the used routing table and route request table. AODV use to use the destination sequence number which results in a reduction of packet size while LOAD does not use it, and it keeps the route discovery process simple. LOAD ensures a loop-free condition by replying for the Route Request (RREQ) message only from the destination node. Moreover, to determine the strongest route, it uses Acknowledge (ACK) message to ensure guaranteed delivery of packets [25]. Similar to the group of protocols such as RPL, M-LOAD, S-AODV and DYMO-Low protocols, it is found that RREP message is utilised to indicate the link breakage in the networks, while the other protocols have not utilised this feature. However, the use of sequence number elides loop freedom in RPL, DYMO-Low and M-LOAD whereas it is not adopted in other protocols. However, Broadcasting of RREQ for route discovery is used in RPL, MLOAD, LOAD, DYMO-Low, SPN and Hi-Low whereas it is not used in other protocols as well [25]. The concept of hop count is used as a routing metric in RPL, MLOAD, Hi-Low, I-Low and S-AODV. The Hello message is used only in the RPL, I-Low and DYMO-Low to KEEP tracking the information about neighbouring nodes. A route recovery process called local repair is adopted in RPL and LOAD Whenever there is a break in the link of the network, this process is adopted to determine alternate links for data forwarding. The mobility support has appeared in all protocols except HiLow and SPEED. [28] Scalability impact can be noticed as a high level for RPL, SPN, HiLow, TA-HiLow and I-Low while AODV is in

Table 2.1: Comparison of the current IOT routing protocols.

Related Work	Number of Nodes	Topology	Environment	Results
OFV and MRHOF [104]	(1) Receiver and (40, 80, 100 and 200) senders	Random	Static	OFV provide lowest performances in all scenarios
OFV and MRHOF [105]	(25, 49 and 81)	Grid and Random	Mobile and Static	MRHOF is more consistent and OFV consume less power. Also, OFV delivers faster convergence time
OFV and MRHOF [106]	(20, 30, 40 and 45)	Grid and Random	Static	OFV and MRHOF performances better with an RX = 60%
OFV and MRHOF [107]	(20, 40, 60 and 80)	Grid and Random	Static	MRHOF performances level is best performing with heavy density like OFV are.
OFV, MRHOF, Energy and MRHOF, ETX [124]	(20, 40, 60, 80, 100, 120 and 140)	Random	Static	MRHOF performance better with low density
MRHOF, ETX	(11, 16, 21, 26, 31, 36, 41 and 46)	Random	Static	MRHOF, ETX consumes more power and it is affected by the network size.
OFV [108]	(1, 5 and 10) Receiver, (35) Sender	Random	Static	Performances of ETX in the network is better than HC in relations of energy consumption, Throughput and PDR
HC and ETX [109]	1 sink 25, 49, 81 senders	Grid and Random	Static and Mobile	MRHOF performances level is not performing well like OFV in terms of duty cycle and convergence time as well as in PC
HC, ETX, XRP, PEP [111]	100	Grid	Static	XRP is more efficient in terms of the packet drop rate and control messages reduction as well as in terms of increasing convergence
OFV and MRHOF [118]	10, 20, 30	Grid, Random manual and Linear	Mobile and Static	MRHOF performance better once static is applied, OFV performance better once mobility is applied. All distributions have same results except linear
OFV and MRHOF [112]	(1) receiver, (19) senders and (1) malicious node	Random	Static	APC increased once malicious is used
OFV and MRHOF [113]	20, 30, 40	Random	Static	The PDR increased while the PC decreases

Medium level and the rest of protocols are performed with a low level of scalability. Furthermore, Path Quality Indication (PQI) is an active routing parameter in RPL and SPN protocols but not on other protocols. Convergence to varying topology is appeared to be slow in SPN, SPEED and HiLow while it is not slow in other protocols [29]. Based on the comparison which the summaries in Table 2.1. All routing protocols are designed with low energy consumption. However, RPL is winning it, competitors, with other protocols, for it is completeness features that make RPL a standard routing protocol for IoT. Accordingly, the RPL ability to connect directly to Internet nodes with global IPv6 addresses is given RPL a high mark and huge research efforts are working on RPL performance. These comprehensive features introduce RPL as a unique protocol with very flexibility to deploy it for different applications' requirements. RPL discards the need to broadcast RREQ messages because it builds the topology proactively, these types of messages are used in several AODV-based protocols. Also, RPL combines the source routing paradigms as well as the distance-vector and supports local and global repair too, this type of support provides the ability to adopt with fault-tolerant applications. In Table 2.1, a detailed comparison regarding IoT routing protocols is presented which critically reflect the main issues and key findings regarding existing research work.

2.6.1 The Performance evaluation of RPL using single and multiple gateways

Many performance evaluation studies of RPL have been introduced by the authors in [42] which evaluate the packet loss, packet end-to-end delay and power consumption. However, the authors did not explore how the average power transmission affects the packet delivery ratio. The authors in [35] have shown extensive experiments on RPL by analyzing the data collection performance and topology stability of RPL. The study in [37] has been investigated widely where two large wireless sensory network platforms have been covered in terms of packet delivery ratio, packet overhead, and packet dynamicity where the node may join or disjoin the network. Through different experimentations, the authors demonstrated the failure of a few nodes affected the stability of the routing structure. Author in [38-39] extended the RPL protocol

to achieve energy efficiency, reliability and low delay data transfer. The authors highlighted that multi-path routing, load balancing and multiple sinks had a great impact once it is merged with the RPL.

2.6.2 RPL with Load balancing

In RPL load balancing makes the traffic as uniform as possible whilst reducing the power consumption of the nodes [40]. There have been numerous attempts to achieve balance in traffic forwarding to decrease congestion and packet drops. In addition, many routing metrics and objective functions have been proposed for the RPL routing protocol in LLNs and 6LoWPAN networks to provide a balanced tree in RPL.

2.6.2.1 RPL Load balancing using multiple gateways

Increasing the number of gateways allows increasing the lifetime of the network together with load balancing. One of these proposals has been studied in [36]. The authors investigated the load balancing problem with multiple gateways and proposed the MLEQ to reduce traffic congestion. Their load balancing scheme has been implemented using network simulators-2 (ns-2) simulator, which is verified by extensive simulation's comparisons. As the proposed MLEQ performance with RPL, the results showed that network throughput and capacity could increase linearly with the number of gateways. Similarly, the authors presented SYN-RPL. It extended RPL to provide an object with multiple gateway networks. A dynamic solution can be employed whenever a gateway fails by finding a new route towards an active gateway. Such flows redirection remains transparent to remote peers. The SYN-RPL has been evaluated using several experimentation's over a real testbed.

2.6.2.2 RPL Load balancing using a single gateway

While using the single gateway, many routing metrics and objective functions have been proposed to be used within the RPL routing protocol in LLNs and 6LoWPAN networks to provide a balanced tree in RPL. The author in [41] proposed a load-balanced routing protocol based on the RPL protocol, called LB-RPL. It detects workload imbalance in a distributed and non-intrusive fashion to achieve balanced workload distribution in the network. This solution is working via signalling techniques, where nodes with heavy traffic represent their status by delaying the transmission of DODAG Information Object (DIO) messages, then a node will be able to detect the queue utilization information of their neighbours and spread out data among the candidate parents. Load Balancing for RPL (LB-RPL) improves the load balancing performance of RPL only by tackling the load balancing problem

in a single gateway network. The main problem with this method is that every node has to forward any traffic coming from its sub-tree based on its current topology. In addition, the LB-RPL was only tested on the ns-2 simulator. Some recent works [43] and [44] have optimized the network lifetime by designing new OFs which consider combining two metrics. The first metric mentioned choosing links with good quality; whereas the second metric mentioned another point which is the residual energy concept. The second metric was used by [43] and [44]. The authors in [43] have proposed a metric focused on the energy consumption of the bottleneck nodes. It also considered parameters such as link data rate, different power transmission, and link qualities. While the authors in [44] have proposed a metric as an adoptive parent node selection mechanism where residual energy, as well as queue utilization of neighbouring nodes, have been considered. Recently, Kim et al., [33] proposed Queue Utilization RPL (QU-RPL) for load balancing under heavy traffic. QU-RPL considers the queue utilization of neighbouring nodes when selecting parent nodes. The authors further described the number of packets in the queue divided by total queue size as queue utilization factor (QU). On other hand, in QU-RPL, the ETX of nodes are not considered while selecting the preferred parent node.

2.7 Load Balancing Protocols

In the study [41], a new load balancing mechanism was optimized called LB-RPL, it amplified the queue utilization to allow a node to arrange its parent candidates. However, when the congestion occurred, a delay was noticed for distributing the routing information which was collected from the base of the neighbour nodes. The authors in [33] showed their interest to solve the load balancing issue under heavy traffic scenarios. They merged the standard objective function zero and queue information to support RPL routing to be balanced under heavy data traffic. The main restriction on their study was the use of OF0, which is not suitable for large density and dynamic IoT networks. This research mention that QU-RPL has the advantage of improving queue losses and PDR. Although, QU-RPL does not support the hybrid network as well as it increases the control overhead packet.

2.7.1 Congestion-Aware Protocol

The authors in [51] tackled the congestion problem and proposed the congestion-aware objective function called CA- OF to deal with high data transmission. The buffer occupancy was the main factor in specifying the efficient route in this study. This work focused on avoiding the congestion area, to allow the node to choose the efficient routing where the PDR was the target. On the other hand, the attention

for routing stability had not been covered. The study in [50] handled the congestion problem using the parent selection mechanism by employing the queue utilization and the residual energy metric of neighbouring nodes. The contribution of this study is to provide an effective selecting mechanism for the proper parent node which will reduce the queue congestion and more residual energy than others. The experiments of the network simulator were carried out using the Cooja simulator under random and grid topology. The results showed a superior routing performance in terms of and PDR and power consumption. The authors in [38] approached another congestion solution called M-RPL which delivered two preferred parent nodes when neighbouring nodes distributed the traffic towards the parent using the control messages of RPL. Therefore, a mechanism with more than one preferred parent will increase the chances to avoid congestion. The authors in [39] provided a new routing metric to discover bottlenecks for each path toward the root. They used parent rank as well as ETX for rank computation. While the authors in [40] presented a mechanism to provide a stable network. The new mechanism estimated the amount of traffic on a node by taking the traffic as a main factor in the routing process. However, the mechanism was feasible for all traffic conditions because it worked with bidirectional and symmetric links only. From the above limitations, these previous contributions do not provide an efficient route that handles load balancing and the congestion problem in burst traffic scenarios. Moreover, the response to these problems in terms of routing information updates is very slow. Moreover, the main issue where the frequent parent switching is carried out is the overhead on the network and to solve this problem, this research also proposes a load balancing and congestion-aware metric under burst traffic scenarios.

Chapter 3

IPv6 Routing protocol for low power and lossy networks (RPL) with Load balancing (Burst Traffic Scenarios)

3.1 Introduction

In recent years, billions of sensors have been deployed across the world, where our world become a sophisticated network called Internet-of-Things (IoT) network [28]. The network including an important field such as health-care, industry, agriculture and transportation are comprised of IoT network features such as large scale, automated and IP based networks, which play an important role to provide a new type of quality of services (QoS) for making the environment much smart and flexible [28]. Moreover, the integration of a large number of nodes with IoT features has become a very hot topic, regarding these issues the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) supports introducing standard RPL policies, which can specify research areas to guide the IoT vision [29]. Routing Over Low Power and Lossy Networks (ROLL) is an IETF working group, which mainly focus to organize the routing of Low Power and Lossy Networks (LLN). The main objective of LLN is to keep the routers and their interconnection more robustly and flexibly. The IETF ROLL working group has worked together, to publish a standard IETF RFC 6550 which is called RPL designed for LLNs. However, the RPL is a distance vector routing protocol which is a suitable scheme for the IoT based LLN, the essential aspect of RPL is the Objective Function (OF), which defines the method that is usually used to calculate the nodes rank by utilizing one or more metric and constraint [30]. In the structure of the RPL standard, the OF is the core of the RPL mechanisms which is responsible

for optimizing the performance of routing in various types of metrics [31]. On the other hand, RPL mainly relies on an OF which is a scalable and flexible algorithm, which manipulates based on the path cost, parent selection and rank calculation. Currently, there are two different OFs introduced for standard RPL. First OF is Minimum Rank with Hysteresis Objective Function (MRHOF). The second OF is Objective Function Zero (OF0). MRHOF can compute node rank built on the additive metrics ETX, latency and hop-count. While OF0 is stated to be a basic OF that does not need any metric to be measured, but it carries a default configuration to minimize hop- count [32].

To dominate the IoT environment there is a need to understand the traffic flow to design a feasible IoT network. There are three types of traffic presented in the current literature including regular, heavy and burst traffic [33]. In the regular delivery, the data is usually collected by the nodes in a continuous bias where less percentage of lost data could have occurred regarding the communication conditions. In the heavy delivery, the data is normally collected based on sink or node interests, which mean the sink or nodes ask for specific information then the sender nodes need to send it. Furthermore, the percentage of lost data raised regarding traffic congestion. In the burst traffic, the data is collected by a powerful sink where massive data are generated in specific time slots. Therefore, a high percentage of lost data can occur in burst traffic regarding load balancing issues [34]. In event-based delivery, sensor nodes, monitor the incidence of events continuously and passively. In this circumstance, the traffic is depending on the distribution of the phenomenon. Burst traffic is one of the IoT application scenarios, where massive data is generated in specific time slots. In certain burst traffic scenarios, the receiving nodes will record a high packet drop probability due to the buffer size limitation problems and congestions. For example, it is common to have a node with relatively higher traffic than neighbouring nodes in RPL, due to the missing load balance feature in RPL [31]. In this case, the parent node can be severely congested and drop many packets due to these limitations. Generally, the burst delivery happens when myriad nodes start sending messages in response to a specific event in a relatively smaller duration of time.

For instance, in a network using RPL with MHROF based on ETX metric, nodes will choose the parents with the best link quality. Considering a network with non-uniform distribution and uneven data traffic may result in a significant load imbalance. The sensor nodes that have links of better quality will forward more packets than others. Thereby, their energy depletion will be notably faster than the nodes with light traffic, and thus, gaps and holes in the network will appear, reducing the network lifetime [34]. Followed by IoT literature, the RPL and its OF were primarily targeting only low power and lossy network, it is found a serious

load balancing problem in a network once heavy traffic load applied within RPL. Therefore, more complicated load balancing issues will create alarming situations during the event of burst traffic load [33]. As load-balancing become an issue in the RPL, some efforts have been discussed for the load balancing problem using multiple gateways to spread the load of the traffic to more than one sink [36]. On the other hand, there is significant research published regarding the efforts targeting RPL Load Balancing in a single gateway by using either new composed or changed metrics [34], [37], [38], [39], [40] and [40].

However, the load balancing problem has been investigated using multiple gateways in [36]. The author has proposed Multi- gateway Load Balancing Scheme for Equilibrium (MLEQ) and compared its performance to RPL. However, they reduce traffic congestion only by supporting additional gateways and do not address the load balancing problem in LLN with a single gateway. The authors in [40] and [33] have tackled the load balancing problem in a single gateway network. Load balancing of RPL (LB-RPL) is proposed to improve load balancing performance of RPL by considering two optimization points including link-layer communication qualities and workload distribution. While in [33] QU-RPL allows a node to rank its parent candidates depending on their queue utilization (QU), but QU-RPL never considers the parent count number to select the parent set. Moreover, the control overhead needs to be reduced to get a fair average of energy by adjusting the RPL parameters.

In this chapter, the major aim is to mainly focus on two important aspects of IoT networks including packet delivery ratio and network lifetime using a new load balancing mechanism for burst traffic load called Expected Transmission Count and Parent Count (ETXPC-RPL). Also compared the performance of RPL in an LLN with a single gateway using OF0 and MRHOF. The study showed that a serious load balancing problem appears in RPL in terms of routing parent selection and most of the packet losses under burst traffic areas due to congestion. This work has utilized the MRHOF to optimize the RPL routing protocol to propose the new mechanism. The main contribution of our proposed mechanism is to improve the packet delivery ratio and lower the power consumption compared to the performance of OF0 and MRHOF. Our simulation results show that the ETXPC-RPL algorithm minimizes packet discard counts and the channel collision through the parent selection mechanism. The main contributions of this chapter can be summarized as follow: To the best of our knowledge, the proposed work is the first to present performance modelling of RPL with burst delivery mode; Study the effect of MRHOF and OF0 on the significant performance of RPL routing protocol under burst traffic load; A novel load balancing routing protocol is proposed on the existing RPL protocol to support RPL routing under burst traffic load called ETXPC-RPL.

The rest of the chapter is organized as Section 2 mentions the related work.

Section 3 defines our proposed ETXPC-RPL protocol. In Section 4, In this work author also presents performance evolution and enhancement. Section 5 shows an analysis of the mean packet delay and buffer overflowprobability with different burst parameters. Section 6 shows the simulation result with three different cases studies. In Section 7 conclude our work.

3.2 LOAD BALANCING PROBLEM WITH RPL PROTOCOL FOR BURST TRAFFIC

RPL achieves routing in a distributed way, where it can be adopted for LLNs but without load balancing, which means this feature is missing in RPL [33]. A major load imbalance occurs for sensor nodes that have more neighbours than others as irregular data traffic and the non-uniform in large-scale LLNs. This causes missing of network connectivity in the whole network because the gaps appear during the routing. This is the reason behind running down the energy faster in the heavy workload [34]. A major problem in LLNs is the network connectivity in terms of load balancing, where different parameters influence the routing in LLNs [45], such as network, node, and link.

RPL traffic depends on the underlying application area, for instance, building monitoring, tracking natural disasters, sporting events to name a few. In these application areas, traffic patterns can either be regular (normal network traffic) or burst (an event triggering the influx of network traffic, recording an infrequent event). The type of routing mechanism is also influenced based on the application area. The distribution of traffic in the network influences the packet delivery ratio and energy consumption involved in forwarding data in the network [40]. Thus, load balancing is a necessary factor that needs to be considered in designing the RPL routing protocol. The most common routing metric which has been fitted with the RPL routing protocol is ETX. It is a communication quality metric to provide a useful connection between two nodes. This is why the author has selected RPL which relies on an OF. It is a scalable and flexible algorithm that is constructed based on three main concepts including the path cost calculation, the Parent selection and the Rank calculation [37]. This flexibility in the OFs keep RPL capable for any application scenarios including burst traffic but OFs need to be adjusted based on the network environment and scenarios, then a new specific OF or metric can be specially implemented for burst traffic [32].

3.3 ETXPC-RPL PROPOSED PROTOCOL

From the RPL operation, it can be recognized that RPL identifies the best paths to route packets through the network according to the OF and a set of metrics as described in the previous section. These metrics can be either node attributes, such as hop-count, remaining node energy; or link attributes, such as link quality, latency, and Expected Transmission Count. A default metric defined MRHOF as the standard metric for RPL by IETF RFC 6719, which is used in most RPL implementations, uses the ETX of links to calculate the path with minimum cost. A Destination Oriented Directed Acyclic Graph (DODAG) created using MRHOF with the ETX metric, nodes tend to select parents with best link quality and smallest hop-count to the root node. In addition to this, hop count, energy level is also used metrics/constraints. However, none of the existing OFs has considered ETX and parent account as a metric to support all types of traffic load [34].

This section presents the proposed scheme OF RPL load balancing problem which dynamically updates RPL based on packet delivery ratio (PDR) and the power consumption (PC) on MRHOF metric to fix the RPL load balancing problem. The proposed scheme utilizes MRHOF to be used in every packet of RPL traffic during the burst traffic scenarios. Therefore, to compute the best path to the root, this research has utilized MRHOF by employing both the ETX value and parent count; where, ETX values are considered as the key items in our metric. Similarly, to the MRHOF in RPL [8], where proposed work uses a hysteresis mechanism to provide stability condition as described in Equation below. ETX (K,pk) is measured by node K which is a link quality indicator between both node K and its parent candidate pk.

$$ETX(K, PK) = \frac{\text{totaltransmissionsfromKtopk}}{\text{successfultransmissionsfromKtopk}} \quad (3.1)$$

The proposed ETXPC-RPL algorithm ?? utilized manipulation of ETX with aggregate values of parent count, each node advertises a Parent Set rather than a single parent to the sink. In RPL control message DIO (DODAG Information Object), where the MinHopRankIncrease parameters are used as defined in [31] in proposed algorithm, where the parent count metric is considered only if the ETX delta between two candidate parents is smaller than MinHopRankIncrease value. To achieve a load balancing under burst traffic by utilizing more nodes as the preferred parent. Also compare the number of parent counts via selecting the one with minimum parent count as the preferred parent. After doing this, more nodes will have a chance to be selected as a preferred parent even their ETX values are not the best. This research proposes a new load balancing mechanism for the RPL protocol

that has multi-hop data collection applications, such as environmental monitoring in the critical event (sport, disaster, festivals). Our scheme is starting with a traffic manager to update the traffic route analyzing the traffic and discover the delivery mode which could be regular or burst, then it will employ threshold of the ETX value and parent count (the number of candidate parents) to compute and detect the most efficient path to the sink. Our traffic management offers functionality to avoid the congestion.

3.4 PERFORMANCE EVOLUTION AND ENHANCEMENT

This chapter will tackle the load balancing problem of RPL. The author has provided an experimental measurement analysis of RPL in high traffic scenarios using the Cooja simulator environment within LN.

Algorithm 1 The proposed load balance algorithm.

procedure INPUT(*ReceivedDIORank*, *ETX*, *ParentID*,) {Parent Count}

M1 =ETX; M2= Parent Count; initialization;

Current Node Recived DIO;

if $M1 \geq M2$ *Then then*

 Calculate the Rank based on the ETX (M1);

 Calculate the Rank based on the number of (M2)

if $A \neq \text{MinHopRankIncreaseValue}$ *Then then*

 use the Values of M1 and M2 if both equal;

 return M2; Selected Parent for node n

while $(M1 \geq M2)$ *then do* {Threshold values}

 use the threshold $A = M2 - M1$;

if *Then then*

$A \neq \text{MinHopRankIncrease Value}$) use the Values of M1 and M2

 if both equal; return M1; Selected Parent for node

As a result, the main focus is to identify that most packet losses under burst traffic areas are due to congestion and that there exists a serious load balancing problem in RPL in terms of routing parent selection via burst scenarios. To solve this problem, this research also introduces an enhancement to improve the performance

of RPL that significantly improves the packet delivery ratio performance with less power consumption by balancing the traffic load within a routing tree considering the parent count number.

3.4.1 Simulation and Network Setup

Cooja simulator has been selected for use as it is a tool for software development in WSN and provides a useful method to set the best environment needs [42]. In our study, the simulated a network with a scenario where only a single sink node is located at the middle top. Also, random topology has been chosen to spread the nodes in a squared area within 1000 meters. In Table 3.1, the Proposed research has designed an RPL network using OF0, MRHOF and ETXPC-RPL by setting the network with 30 nodes. The experiments have been conducted under different traffic load networks containing (1, 20, 40 and 60 PPS/node) which include regular traffic and burst traffic with random middle topology. This work has investigated the RPL performance in terms of two measurements including packet delivery ratio and power consumption.

3.4.2 Experiment results

The experiment results have been collected considering various traffic load networks (1, 20, 40, and 60 PPS/node) within random middle topologies, and the proposed work also observed the performance of RPL for different metrics MRHOF, OF0 and ETXPC. This study sets the sink in the middle top and study the RPL behaviour in terms of PDR and PC.

Figure 3.1: The network window (Sink located in the middle top).

Table 3.1: Simulations Parameters

Parameters	Values
Objective Function (OF)	OF0, MRHOF, ETXPC
Traffic Load (PPS)	1, 20, 40, 60
Density Network	30 Motes
Sink Location	Middle Top
TX Ratio	100%
TX Range	100 m
Mote Startup Delays	1.000
Topologies	Random with middle top sink
Simulation Time	900 seconds
Mote Type	Sky Mote

3.4.2.1 Traffic load RPL Performance within MRHOF

Figure 3.2, shows that the PDR value roughly reached 1.0 when traffic load was less than or equal to 40 PPS. This means that the performance of RPL is good for PDR more than 0.98 whenever the traffic load (1 to 40 PPS). The PDR value decreases once the traffic load is under burst traffic (60 or more). Figure 3.2 shows the behaviour of the power consumption for the same traffic load. It can be seen that the power consumption value increases in a linear fashion as the traffic load values increase. The average power consumption value is good (approximately 1.19 kilobyte) when traffic load is less than or equal to 40%. While the power consumption is very high for RPL performance within MRHOF under burst Traffic (60 PPS or more). It is consuming about 4.8 kb of energy, which is too high-power consumption compared to regular traffic (less than 40 PPS).

3.4.2.2 The RPL Performance within OF0

Figure 3.3 shows that RPL with OF0 has PDR average similar to the one for MRHOF. The PDR value decreases as the traffic load value increases. PDR value under regular traffic is more than 0.98 whenever the traffic load is between 1 to 40 PPS, while under the burst traffic it is around 0.45 when Traffic Load is equal to 60 or more. Figure 3.4 presents the behaviour of the power consumption for the same traffic load. It is quite similar to the power consumption values when MRHOF is used. Where the power consumption value increases steadily as the traffic load value increases during regular Traffic Load with a good average (approximately 1.3 kilobytes). In addition, also observed that the average power consumption is high

Figure 3.2: The PDR and PC values for MRHOF in 30 nodes using random topology

(approximately 5.1 kilobytes) when burst traffic load is applied. It is too high-power consumption value compared to its value in the burst traffic with MRHOF.

Figure 3.3: The PDR and PC values for OF0 in 30 nodes using random topology

3.4.2.3 Enhancement RPL within ETX and Parent Count (ETXPC)

In Figure 3.5 an ETXPC has been used and found that the average PDR of RPL performance is around 0.99. Also, the PDR of ETXPC is almost used for both types of traffic load including regular and burst traffic load with values more than 0.98 Figure 3.5 The proposed work used ETXPC to signify the average power consumption. Indeed, the results are showing a fair power consumption especially for the

Figure 3.4: The PDR and PC values for ETXPC in 30 nodes using random topology

burst Traffic Load with a value of about 4 kilobytes. Also, the average packet delivery ratio is fair too with ETXPC. The result shows that the performance of RPL using our ETXPC provides an improved behaviour where a load balancing feature is applied under critical conditions such as burst traffic.

RESULTS DISCUSSION

3.4.3 The impact of the objective function metrics OF0, MRHOF and ETXPC

From the presented results, it can be observed that without the load balancing features in the RPL routing. The value of traffic load is very volatile above 60. RPL with MRHOF and OF0 has poor performance while delivering the burst Traffic messages of the LLN. The results in Figure 3.5 have shown that the performance of RPL is very similar for MRHOF, OF0 and ETXPC under regular traffic which is given a good PDR around 0.98, while ETXPC outperforms both OF0 and MRHOF under burst traffic Load with 1, 0.996793 and 0.980636 respectively. Also, the results show that ETXPC consumes less power compared to OF0 and MRHOF with values 4, 5.1 and 4.8 kb respectively. It was observed from the simulation results that the ETXPC enhances the RPL routing protocol in terms of PDR and power consumption using a load balance mechanism to support the RPL performance under burst traffic load.

3.4.4 Burst Load Balancing Analysis

This study gathered the results of our simulations using various data generation rates including burst traffic load, such as 1 packet per 1 minute scenario, 20 packet per 1 minute scenario, 40 packet per 1 minute scenario, Packet per 1 minute scenario (burst traffic).

Figure 3.5: PDR Values for MRHOF, OF0 and ETXPC under different Traffic Load.

Figure 3.6: PC Values for MRHOF, OF0 and ETXPC under different Traffic Load.

To explore the burst delivery in the simulated network, also to design the workload into a total number of forwarded packets from each sensor node. Figure 3.5 and Figure 3.6 show the impact average of PDR and power consumption values for MRHOF, OF0 and ETXPC using different scenarios. Fig 6 shows that a good PDR

average is achieved with three scenarios 1, 2 and 3 for MRHOF, OF0 and ETXPC. While in scenario 4 (burst traffic) the PDR value has decreased rapidly during it was used with MRHOF or OF0 which means both algorithms are not performing well for burst traffic scenarios, while ETXPC offers a good PDR value with the same scenario. This means that the newly proposed mechanism has worked with burst Traffic where the number of parent counts has been considered during the load balancing process. Fig.3.6 presents the average of the power consumption value for MRHOF, OF0 and ETXPC using different scenarios. An accepted power consumption average has been achieved with three scenarios 1, 2 and 3 for MRHOF, OF0 and ETXPC. However, ETXPC uses the highest power consumption value among these scenarios. While in scenario 4 (burst traffic) the PC value increases suddenly with the use of MRHOF, OF0 or ETXPC for burst Traffic scenario.

CONCLUSION This chapter address the load balancing problem of RPL routing protocol under burst traffic using a single gateway. With simulation experiments, in addition to this, an empirically identified that standard RPL is not able to hold the burst traffic load. To address this issue, the author proposes a new load balancing protocol, called ETXPC-RPL, which consist of the ETX metric and the number of parent nodes for selecting the best parent. With this two-metric combination, the load is balanced in the network under burst traffic load. Also considered different traffic scenarios, the located sink, and the single gateway. To prevent the problem of RPL when burst traffic load occurs in the IoT network causing the network with high packet losses and stability problems. the performance of RPL is good for PDR more than 0.98 whenever the traffic load (1 to 40 PPS). It can be seen that the power consumption value increases in a linear fashion as the traffic load values increase. The average power consumption value is good (approximately 1.19 kilobyte) when traffic load is less than or equal to 40%. PDR value under regular traffic is more than 0.98 whenever the traffic load is between 1 to 40 PPS. Based on our results, the proposed algorithm ??is useful for RPL to hold the burst traffic scenarios. This work will extend our contribution to improving our algorithm, considering more metrics and more parameters including transmission range and density network using extensive simulations.

Chapter 4

A Burst and Congestion-Aware Routing Metric for RPL Protocol in IoT network

$$F = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{P+R}} \quad (4.1)$$

4.1 Introduction

In routing protocol for low power and lossy networks (RPL) load balancing is managed by using a route request technique that selects the efficient path without dealing with the congested area. However, in a burst traffic scenario, multiple sensor nodes in a network start generating high data packet rates which cause congestion. Thus, packet overflow at buffer nodes occurs in the network [46]. The performance of RPL on an evaluation and analysis basis has been studied intensively in the literature with varying scenarios and network setups. In the study [35] the authors perform an extensive experiment to analyse the performance of the RPL routing protocol in terms of topology stability. Similarly, the authors in [38] evaluate the RPL performance using the data collection model, the author compares the results with the Collection Tree Protocol (CTP), the comparison shows that RPL has better performance in terms of Packet Reception Ratio (PRR) and power consumption. The study in [47] investigates the two standard RPL objective functions using different density networks, in terms of PDR and power consumption, where each node is placed under random and grid topology. Through different experimentations, the authors demonstrate the packet reception ratio affected the performance of the routing structure. Similarly, the authors in [48] survey the RPL with exhaustive information on building RPL routing protocol, objective function, DODAG models, and the best route

selection for nodes in Low Power and Lossy Networks (LLNs). Since traffic congestion causes remarkable issues for IoT networks, supporting a burst traffic network with a load balancing feature can help to mitigate the impact. This study can leverage IoT to drive venue efficiency in burst traffic networks through several initiatives such as traffic management, building performance, and stadium security to improve the game-day experience as shown in Figure 4.1. In our study, the proposed work also monitor all building systems from a centralized area to track metrics such as energy costs and optimize building performance using different network density. This will help people enter and exit the venue, find parking, and navigate to various parts of the stadium by using mobile apps, cameras, and sensors especially in peak time when congestion occurs. In this study, through simulation of bust traffic scenario, research demonstrates high packet loss and power consumption with the standard RPL with OF0. This study also introduced an effective improvement to support the RPL congestion technique by switching the parent node, and the load balancing technique by considering the number of packets in the parent selection algorithm. The rest of the chapter is organized as follow. Section II mentions the background and related work. Section III defines the problem with the RPL protocol for burst traffic. In Section IV, this research presents our solution. Section V shows performance evolution and enhancement. In Section VI, overall performance is calculated in the burst traffic scenarios even in the high-density network. This work also focused on reducing the packet loss as well as the power consumption within a good PDR in LLN, two techniques were also used such as avoiding work.

4.2 PROBLEM WITH RPL PROTOCOL FOR BURST TRAFFIC

RPL fails to distribute traffic load with the best path while a burst mode is applied, it is regarding the missing of the load balancing features [54]. RPL is classified as a single path routing protocol and in this case, the nodes will transmit packets directly to the preferred parent [64]. Unfortunately, in burst traffic scenarios, the networks need to choose links to build a new topology regarding the number of times that a set of nodes will switch their preferred parents repeatedly to address the load balancing issue. This will cause congestion and unnecessary costs. Therefore, this study proposes a congestion-aware routing metric that is a composite of three metrics including OF0, rank, and the number of received packets. The RPL routing protocol was designed for handling the low power and lossy network, there are several features still missing and need to be covered such as self-healing mechanism as well as load balancing. Regarding this fact, RPL is not able to show the capability

Figure 4.1: Architecture of stadium and sports event automation control system.

to support a network with burst traffic, which mean, once the traffic rate becomes at a high level during burst mode, then RPL will not be able to handle it as it should be, comparing to the regular traffic. Regarding this issue, the IoT network with RPL routing protocol will suffer from many problems consisting of load imbalance and congestion, where a high packet loss and high-power consumption will be generated. The problem becomes complicated in burst traffic when the network density is increased.

Figure 4.2 presents an example of a congestion avoiding technique, when a network is suffering from instability, which is caused once nodes start switching their preferred parent without any methods to check the traffic load in advance to reach load balancing. In the first RPL tree, seven nodes have been selected to build the network, where only one node is a source node (S) and six other nodes are destination nodes. Four nodes from the six nodes have selected node number 1, with a smaller number of packets when it received DIO from it. However, in the second RPL tree, a new DIO from node 1 with updated routing table information causes all the four nodes to change the preferred parent to node number 6, which has a smaller number of packets than node 1. It becomes a loop in a switching parent whenever the neighbour's nodes receive a new DIO which ensues load alternation

but with no balancing.

Figure 4.2: An example of the congestion avoiding technique.

4.3 PROPOSED SOLUTION

This study has solved the load balancing and congestion problem in the RPL routing protocol under burst traffic networks. Then introduced a new lexically metric called BCA- RPL (Load Balancing and Congestion Aware for RPL Routing Protocol). The proposed metric applies a load balancing using the hop-count metric as a primary metric to compute the rank. Also, to provide a parent selection mechanism for each node to select its neighbour's node as candidate parent; whenever the candidate parent set is selected, the second metric focus on switching to another parent concerning the number of packets received from neighbours to avoid the congestion area.

4.3.1 The Load-Balancing Technique

In the RPL routing process, nodes are sending a packet to another node including routing information to build the RPL DODAG [56]. The routing information includes ID node, queue size, received packet, and power, among others. Also, each node receives a specific number of packets from the neighbour nodes during this procedure is part of the load balancing technique [57]. Based on this monitor the number of packets to assess the traffic load is an important factor in choosing an efficient route. This study also provides a proper arrangement to compute the path with exact intervals. In this case, this research will build the path every time based on the present value of the traffic load for the nodes with less power consumption, each time the node is sending a packet. Based on an efficient route to control the traffic load whenever the number of packets on a path increase. Thus, the link efficiency of the initial optimal path needs to be adjusted with the traffic load information on the path. Therefore, this study provides a technique to compute the path dynamically on exact time based on the number of packets. The traffic size of each node becomes balanced via the network by distributing the traffic across all the neighbour nodes with a smaller number of packets.

4.3.1.1 The Congestion Avoiding Technique and Parent Selection

Proposed scheme avoids the bottlenecks area in a burst traffic scenario. The proposed OF lexically combines the hop count with the traffic indicator metric (TrafficInd). The hop count metric is employed by a node to select candidate parents and then the traffic indicator metric is used to apply the load balancing technique in case of having more than one candidate parent in the parent set. Figure 4.3 showed a flow chart of the BCA- RPL implementation over RPL. In this section, the proposed study describes the implementation of the load balancing technique and merge it with the congestion avoiding of the high packet stream nodes over the standard RPL routing protocol using the OF0. The steps of our proposed algorithm for the parent selection procedure are shown in Algorithm 2. The traffickInd metric is calculated by each node to consider the number of received packets from its children over a specified period. To implement BCA-RPL, several enhancements have been made to the standard RPL routing protocol. These enhancements are mentioned as steps in the following: Stage 1: whenever any node in the network sends a message to another node, the sender node must check the information of its routing table to find a route towards the destination node. In this case, if the path is available in the routing table then S will send the message to the neighboured node. If it is not available in the routing table then the message stays in a queue. Also, the S node starts to send DIS to its neighbours to initiate the discovery process. Stage 2: This

study has reduced the number of packets loss of the node that is involved in building the RPL DODAG tree based on the congestion avoiding technique. However, the PDR of these nodes should be enough to send the data packet over burst traffic to reach the following neighbour in the path. Stage 3: to merge the load balancing technique with the congestion avoidance technique, this research applies a method before sending the messages to the following hop. This process checks the number of packets of the sender node. If the number of packets in the node is relatively high, then the process will turn into another candidate node to avoid congestion. After doing this, the current path is deleted from the routing table. This leads the S node to initiate the discovery process again using the DIO messages and find a new path to the node to achieve load balancing.

Figure 4.3: Flow Chart of the new technique over the RPL

4.4 PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

This study evaluated the RPL routing protocol and optimize it in terms of packet loss, power consumption and PDR. RPL performance is analysed after extensive

Algorithm 2 Selection of the Best Parent Algorithm

procedure CONGESTION AVOIDING($\{\}$) This is a test

Input: $A1, A2$ (two candidate parents)

Read the value

if $A1$ or $A2 = BP$ **then then**

do d $A1$ or $A2$ is Best Parent

if $A1.Rank = A2.Rank$ **then then**

Return $A1$ z then

if $A1.TraicInd \leq A2.TraicInd$ **then then**

Return $A1$ or BP

if $A1.Rank > A2.Rank$ **then then**

Return $P1$

if $A1.A1.Rank = A2.Rank$ **then then**

Return $A1$ or BP

if $Condition \geq 1$ **then then**

Return $A1$ or $A2$ D Consider number of packets

else

Do otherwise

while $A1.TraicInd < A2.TraicInd$ **then do** {else statement runs}

Return $A1$ or $A2$ D Consider number of packets

Table 4.1: Simulations Parameters

Parameters	Values
Objective Function (OF)	OF0, MRHOF, ETXPC
Traffic Load (PPS)	1, 20, 40, 60
Density Network	30 Motes
Sink Location	Middle Top
TX Ratio	100%
TX Range	100 m
Mote Startup Delays	1.000
Topologies	Random with middle top sink
Simulation Time	900 seconds
Mote Type	Sky Mote

experimentation using the Cooja simulator on the Contiki operating system. The simulator results showed that the congestion and unbalanced traffic are increased in the burst traffic scenarios, especially when the high-density network is increased.

4.4.1 Simulation Environment Setup

This work uses the standard IoT simulator, called Cooja simulator, it is been known as a very suitable tool for IoT network development. To run our scenario, this study used the SKY mote type to build a network with one source node (sink) located in the point of (50, 50) and the remaining destination nodes (sender) are distributed randomly, all the nodes are distributed within 1000 meters in a squared area. As in Table 4.1 proposed work employed two metrics in our RPL network including OF0-RPL and BCA-RPL to compare the standard OF-RPL with the enhanced BCA-RPL. Also, the network consists of different densities of nodes (10, 20, 30, 40, 50) the experiments have been verified in a burst traffic scenario with 30 apps.

4.4.2 Results

The simulation results were compiled for experiments with under burst traffic load networks using random typologies. This study evaluated the performance of RPL using OF0-RPL and BCA-RPL. Also located the sink in the middle. The results present the impact of the used metric on the RPL behaviour in terms of packet loss rate, power consumption, and PDR as shown in Figure 4.4. Congestion increases as the density network increases where the problems of packet loss and power consumption will get worse. Therefore, it becomes more complicated to reduce the traffic load balancing opportunities in the network.

4.4.2.1 The RPL packet loss rate within OF0-RPL and BCA-RPL

Figure 4.6 also observed that the packet loss rate increased regularly when the number of nodes increased for both OF0-RPL and BCA-RPL, except for the network with 10 to 20 nodes where the packet loss ratio is zero even in burst traffic. Also, suddenly the packet loss ratio value increases once the density network is 30 nodes or 50 nodes under burst traffic (30 or more). Moreover, a high packet loss is recorded once RPL-OF0 is used in a high-density network with burst traffic scenarios and reached 74% and 91% for 40 and 50 nodes respectively. While these percentages are reduced for the same scenarios to become only 39% and 46% for (40 and 50 nodes respectively) using our new metric BCA-RPL.

Figure 4.4: Simulation Experiment Example with 10 Nodes

4.4.2.2 The RPL power consumption impact within OF0-RPL and BCA-RPL

Figure 4.7, demonstrates the power consumption RPL with BCA-RPL is better than the OF0-RPL - the power consumption increases as network density increases. Also, the results show that the power consumption values of OF0-RPL in a low-density network (10 to 20 nodes) is about 2.75kb to 2.89kb respectively. While it is 2.83 to 2.94 once BCA-RPL is used then 0.98 whenever the burst traffic mode is generated (more than 30 PPS). Moreover, the proposed work also observed that the highest values of power consumption occur once a network with the high-density network of 50 nodes is applied for both OF0-RPL and BCA-RPL, where power consumption values reached 7.32kb for OF0-RPL and 6.08kb for BCA-RPL. It means BCA-RPL is reducing the usage of the power of RPL routing protocol under burst traffic in different density networks, especially in the high-density network.

4.4.2.3 The RPL packet delivery ratio impact within OF0-RPL and BCA-RPL

Figure 4.8, demonstrates the BCA-RPL enhances PDR for OF0- RPL with almost 1.00% PDR for both metrics OF0-RPL and BCA-RPL once 10, 20 and 30 nodes are used under burst traffic. On the other hand, the PDR is suddenly decreased once the number of nodes reaches 40 nodes in both metrics OF0-RPL and BCA-RPL with 0.62% and 0.64% respectively. Similarly, once the number of nodes is increased to 50 nodes, the lowest PDR percentage was recorded with 0.48 and 0.54 for OF0-RPL

Figure 4.5: Simulation Experiment Example with 50 Nodes

and BCA-RPL respectively.

4.5 CONCLUSION

This work has tackled two major issues with RPL: the load balancing and congestion area in the RPL routing protocol under burst traffic networks. To this conclusion, this study introduced a new logically metric called BCA-RPL. The proposed metric applies two techniques, the first technique is the load balancing technique by using the hop-count metric as a primary metric to compute the rank. The second technique is the congestion avoidance technique by switching the best parent selection to avoid the congested area. By extensive experimentation based on the Cooja simulator, demonstrated that BCA-RPL worked efficiently with RPL and attained an enhancement in terms of network packet loss with 50% reduction, power consumption and PDR with an acceptable level of the IoT network. Then compared BCA-RPL and OFO-RPL performance, BCA-RPL performances better than the original OFO-RPL under burst traffic load with different density networks.

Figure 4.6: The packet loss ratio values under different network densities.

Figure 4.7: The power consumption values under different network densities.

Figure 4.8: The PDR values under different network density.

Chapter 5

A New Burst-Traffic Metric for RPL (BT-RPL) in IoT network concerning Packet Reception Ratio

5.1 Introduction

The load balance is controlled by utilizing the route request technique, which is helpful to select the efficient path without using the congested area. Although, in a burst traffic case, various sensor nodes inside the network initiate to send a higher amount of network traffic, which causes congestion. In addition to this, packets overflow over nodes buffer also happens inside that network [46].

There has been widely research carried out in RPL literature on the performance of RPL based on analysis and evaluation. In the studies of [35], various network deployments and designs are also discussed in the detail. The authors have also presented a detailed experimental analysis to evaluate the RPL routing protocols performance concerning topology stability. In addition to this, the authors of [38] also evaluated the RPL performances via the data collection model. The authors also provided the comparative analysis with Collection Tree Protocol (CTP), in the comparison, authors have proved that RPL routing outperformed in terms of Packet Reception Ratio (PRR) and power consumption. The authors of [47] depicted that two different standards of RPL function mainly using various density networks also introduced in the form of packet delivery ratio and power consumption, where the network nodes are configured via random and grid technology. Although, from the evaluations, authors have investigated that packets ratio can affect the routing structure performance. Similarly, the authors of [48] also presented an RPL survey based

on exhaustive building information of RPL routing protocols, objective function and DODAG models are also discussed with the help of burst route selection between LLNs nodes.

However, traffic congestion also causes significant IoT issues inside the IoT network, utilizing the load balance feature can mitigate the network issues. With the help of several initiatives such as traffic management, building performance, and stadium security, are capable to leverage IoT for effective in burst and venue development, this significantly improves the experience of game-day as depicted in Figure 5.1. The proposed studies monitor all the systems which are associated with building from the centralized area, which helps to identify and track the costs and energy consumption, also to optimize the performance of the building by utilizing various network densities. This approach helps the potential fans, which enter and leave their associated venue, find appropriate parking and they can flexibly navigate the different parts of the stadium from mobile apps, cameras and various sensors especially in a busy time. These studies also discuss the delivery mode and engage the threshold of the OF0 values and packets numbers to classify the candidate efficient route set for the source node. These studies also include the congestion avoiding technique and load balancing approaches to optimize the RPL burst traffic scenarios in most of the congestion cases. Our model functionality mainly focuses to avoid bottlenecks area, which arises the significant congestion. Proposed work also evaluate RPL routing protocol performance in RPL-OF0 via LLN, which also compares the overall results with the BCA-RPL concerning packets loss, power consumption and PDR values.

5.2 RPL OBJECTIVE FUNCTION BACKGROUND

5.2.1 RPL standard Objectives Function Design

The major aim of RPL relies on a robust flexible algorithm of an OF, which can be easily manipulated via path cost, parent selection, and the ranks calculation. Recently, two different types of OFs have been proposed that pragmatically represents the RPL as bellow:

5.2.1.1 Minimum Rank with Hysteresis Objective Function (MRHOF)

The (MRHOF) is commonly known as an Objective Function (OF) that utilizes hysteresis during the selection of the smallest values of paths. The authors in [16] have presented various additive metrics that help to implement MRHOF, in which routing objective helps to reduce default routing metrics. One of these nodes must

Figure 5.1: Architecture of Stadium and Sport Event Automation Control System

support at least one metric. However, utilizing MRHOF with the Expected Transmission Count (ETX) metric empowers RPL to identify the minimum and stable ETX paths. Moreover, this OF is mainly utilized for selecting parents who are responsible for delivering the least number of transmissions [16]. In the wireless access point, the ETX metric is the expected transmission number, which is mandatory for smooth transmission and packets acknowledgement on that access point link. This functionality is vital for classifying and separating less reliable paths that utilize larger packets for transmission from best paths. This metric is capable to estimate the transmission number until a message reaches its destination and creating a systematic graph with corresponding values, whenever redundant paths are constructed to manipulate the node isolation [58].

5.2.1.2 Objective Function Zero (OF0)

The (OF0) is capable to identify the preferred node with minimum rank values, which helps to operate via abstracted statistics of RPL DODAG Information Object (DIO) containers. OF0 is created as default OF which enables the different RPL implementation interoperation, due to this reason, standard OF denies specifying how link metrics and nodes are interconnected with increasing Rank and other variables. The major aim of OF0 is to enable a node for joining DODAG Version to

produce a feasible connection for specific nodes set. However, optimization of paths will not be guaranteed for such specific metric alone [58]

5.2.2 Comparison of existing LLN routing protocols

A modern routing strategy is mandatory to provide support to routing constraints and metrics, which helps to maintain and control the data traffic for LLN routing. As a metric is a measurement utilized for best path selection, similarly, a constraint is utilized as an additional measurement to count nodes and links, which are not connected for constraints. Although, constraints and metrics could be nodes link, such as metric link level can cater feasible latency, throughput, and reliability. In addition to this, nodes level metrics can be utilized as energy state of nodes, Hop count, and node attributes for current states. In RPL, there are no specific forwarding policies for any specific metrics due to the fact of low power networks and the difference between the characteristics and requirements, For example, both of these are classified as distinguished in resource constraints. There are a large number of applications such as lossy links, and mobility-based applications [4]. In IETF Drafts, many applications and existing literature can be found. The authors of [16] presented a new robust and optimized load balancing mechanism known as LB-RPL, which is more capable to improve queue buffer utilization so that a node can easily manipulate its parent candidates. Moreover, if congestion occurred then a delay notice will be initiated to equally distribute the routing information, which was acquired from random neighbouring nodes. The authors of [59] also depicted a methodology to resolve the load balancing and congestion problems of larger traffic scenarios. The authors collaboratively combined the standard OF0 and specific routing information, which helps RPL routing metrics for balancing heavy burst traffic. The proposed studies are also limited, such as it only utilizes OF0, and it cannot be implemented in the IoT network with large density data packets. Overall, it can be estimated that the Qu-RPL approach is capable to rectify the queue losses and PDR. Moreover, Qu-RPL is also limited in a hybrid network, which results in heavy processing and memory overhead.

5.2.3 RPL routing protocols extension with multiple parents

5.2.3.1 Load balancing and congestion aware routing protocol

To optimize the time variation adaptability and throughput of traffic load, the authors of [65] have proposed the backpressure model (BRPL), which feasibly switches backpressure routing and RPL routing metrics to classify the best network features.

The BRPL model also manipulates the additional features of mandatory and feasible path selection for solving heavy traffic loads. Moreover, BRPL enables multiple instances for the network, adding to this it also enables the DAG RPL instances with single or multiple DODAGs roots features. The authors of the model have also depicted the RPL topology via multi-topology routing functionality, they have also normalized the RPL protocol of multicommodity function, in which every DAG is interrelated to associated commodity. The BRPL model is based on the DAG routing up forwarding approach, which combines OF ranking with congestion gradient of the network derived from differential queue gradients features. Overall, model performance is evaluated with a real-time based Cooja simulator, experimental results are carried out with FIT IoT Lab testbed [66]. This model utilizes 100 M3 open nodes of Grenoble, specially designed for FIT IoT LAB. Topology is mainly focused on 95 sensors with five major roots. To provide support for the MAC layer, CSMA/CA network driver was also deployed in collaboration with MiMAC attributes, however, the radio duty-cycle of this model was set to a disabling condition. Although, the BRPL model is comparatively depicted with the standard of RPL routing and backpressure routing. The standard RPL and BRPL are capable to utilize the same ETX-OF with the default setting features.

In the evaluation results, traffic burst with a packet loss rate of BRPL achieved 4.5 times lower as compared to RPL, this is due to fact that BRPL flexibly adopts the traffic dynamical rules with the help of the QuickTheta algorithm. In the experiment, the sensing rate of data is kept fixed all time, whereas RPL achieved the higher packet loss rate because RPL always selects the best optimal paths via OF. As BRPL and backpressure routing utilize the sub paths for optimization once traffic load become higher, at this stage lower packet loss and higher throughput is achieved than RPL. Overall, BRPL performs better as compared to backpressure routing concerning end-to-end delay during the minimum traffic load. Although, major routes of backpressure routing depend on congestion gradients, which also suffer from longer end-to-end delays. In the study of [40], the authors have proposed an opportunistic routing protocol (ORPL), which is capable to work with any-any on demanded traffic platform, In addition to this, it also supports downward and upward traffic tactics. In the proposed ORPL, a node broadcasts packets rather than selecting the next hop, then the node propagates the packets to the destination. The next hop is always selected during transmission time in upward routing. However, first neighbour (1) wakes up, then the packet is received by a neighbour (2), then neighbour (3) is defined nearer to root, overall, this systematic pattern is utilized to forward and acknowledge the packet statics. Due to this reason, the forwarding decision mechanism is implemented at top of the receiver rather than the sender location. This is the unique difference that can be observed between

ORPL and opportunistic RPL metrics [67].

The routing downwards mainly depends on the routing set notion, which is a set of sub DODAG nodes utilized for the root node. This approach is responsible for collecting nodes information either on the destination path or vice versa. A node can flexibly send packets to a downwards location, once node (1) successfully initiates, node (2) acknowledges the received packets and node (3) must be placed far away from the rooted node of (4), which comprises of routing a set of destination. To imply any to any traffic packet strategy, a node packet is always routed its common ancestors' upwards location, then to its ancestors downwards direction. The major aim of ORPL is to satisfy the efficiency scalability of memory space via routing thresholds rather than routing table and bloom filters for managing space. However, ORPL feasibly uses the Estimated Duty Cycled wake-ups (EDC) as routing metric [69], which helps to exceed the duty-cycled wakeups turns, which are mandatory for root. EDC methodology is derived from the ETX adoption for the development of energy-efficient anycast routing platforms.

The authors of [70] have pragmatically evaluated the ORPL metrics based on the Indriya testbed, which comprises 135 nodes of telos. The testbed is implemented with ContikiMAC, in which a sender phase-lock approach is used to record the sender's wake-up phase to make the next transmission flexible and smoother. The authors have also extended the ContikiMAC default lock phase from 15 to 63 ms, to deny losing synchronization during long wake-up intervals. Overall results depict that ORPL routing accuracy is better than basic RPL. The authors of [71] presented collection tree protocol (CTP) methodology, similarly authors in [72] depicted, opportunistic routing for WSN (ORW), and authors in [73] have deployed low-power wireless bus (LWB). The aforementioned work is carried via end-to-end-delay, energy-efficient metric energy duty cycle, packet delivery ratio. Overall ORPL metrics outperform the fundamental RPL in terms of one-to-many or any-to-any platforms, these platforms mainly focus on PDR, latency, duty cycles, and throughput. The authors in [74] provided a multipath routing mechanism with the help of load distribution and RPL protocol, this proposed model helps to distribute traffic load in equal weights between the same levels DODAG nodes, traffic distribution is achieved with the help of heuristic load distribution algorithm (HeLD) [74]. A multipath DODAG node maintains a parent set by utilizing Pi DIO messages, which are received from multiple neighbouring nodes.

The authors of the proposed model also developed a cost-effective load distribution problem to deal with the issues associated with the flow. This issue of flow is carried out by utilizing only approximate local network information. The authors developed a heuristic load distribution (HeLD) algorithm, where each node is capable to compare all input traffic rates against the parent's pairwise statistics. If the

input traffic rate does not match to at least two of its parents, then the traffic is processed so that it can match between two parents' nodes rate.

To evaluate the performance of the proposed metric, the authors have presented a comparison against single path RPL and multipath node-disjoint algorithm. The proposed model is carried out with the OMNET++ and MATLAB simulation over the data link layer. In addition to this, CSMA-CA over IEEE802.15.4 standard is also deployed. From overall simulations, the proposed model is capable to optimize the throughput and lifetime of feasible networks rather than other methods. However, this model also produces consistent network link drop due to the fact of the very least reliable link utilization. The authors in [75] have extended the basic RPL with temporary multipath routing support during congestion events on a path. Each node is deployed to identify the congestion with packet delivery ratio (PDR) analysis on received packets. The calculation of PDR values is only achieved once each node comprises the expected data rate statistics for all associated child nodes. Due to this reason, all nodes mainly rely on DIO messages for parent information. A congestion interval (CI) values also decrease less than defined values, whenever the average PDR is deemed congested. When node congestion occurs then a child node receives congestion notification (CN) via periodic DIO message information. Then node propagates the forwarding packets to the original parent or other parent table node, this is achieved only with the help of DIO messages in the response to CN alerts. Each node utilizes CN alerts of neighbours for avoiding forwarding packets to the congested node. If the child node fails to receive CN messages of associated parents, then no more traffic is processed.

The authors have provided a comparison between M-RPL and basic RPL with MRHOF via IEEE 802.15.4 MAC, the Cooja simulation is deployed for performance evaluation. The basic RPL is outperformed by the proposed M-RPL model, M-RPL also utilizes very little energy consumption as compared to RPL. M-RPL also failed in terms of reducing mandatory end to end delays, because M-RPL causes the delay due to a multipath based approach. The authors of [21] depicted the congestion avoidance CA-RPL model with multipath routing. The proposed model is capable to optimize the performance during emergencies event, such as when monitoring statistics for more frequent events are feasible transferred to the sink node. For this objective, authors have developed a new metric function known as minimized delay metric or DELAY_ROOT, which utilizes the cumulative sum of forwarding hop by hop delays on the DODAG node root. The ContikiMAC simulator is utilized to lower down the delay metric assumption via the duty cycling approach. Each node of this mode utilizes the collaborative mechanism of ETX routing features to calculate the nodes paths and weights. Once parent nodes are ranked accordingly associated weights, then the node identifies at least two-parent candidates with the highest

Table 5.1: Researcher papers focusing on RPL OF

Relate Work	Forwarding Packet Single/Multiple parent	Main Enhancement	Routing Metrics & Constraints	Evaluation Metrics and Tools
		Load balancing, congestion, energy		
Ullah et al. [18]	Single Parent	Efficiency Energy Congestion Aware	(ETX), (OF0), (Energy), (QU).	Cooja Simulator
CA-OF [28]	Single Parent	Congestion Aware	(ETX), (BO).	Cooja Simulator
CoAR [21]	Single Parent	Congestion Aware	(ETX), (Energy), (QU).	Cooja Simulator
PC-RPL [19]	Single Parent	Load balancing	(OF0), (RSSI), (ETX).	Real Testbed - CSMA
QU-RPL [17]	Single Parent	Load balancing, Congestion Aware	(OF0), (Energy), (QU), (Delay).	Real Testbed - CSMA
OHCA [20]	Single Parent	Congestion Aware	(ETX), (BO), (Delay).	Cooja Simulation
M-RPL [22]	Multiple parent	Load balancing		Cooja Simulation
ORPL [27] ORPL-LB [32]	Multiple parent	Efficiency scalability of memory space	(OF0), (PC), (Mobility).	Real Testbed - Indriya
BRPL [31]	Multiple parent	Congestion Aware	(ETX), (OF0), (QU), (Mobility), (Delay).	Cooja Simulator
CA-RPL [40]	Multiple parent	Congestion Aware	(ETX), (Delay).	Cooja Simulator

weight's values. After this, packets are mutually distributed over these parents according to weighted paths. The Cooja simulator with ContikiMAC and duty cycling approach is utilized for performance evaluations. Overall results of CA-RPL accuracy stood better than basic RPL in terms of packet reception number (PRN). In addition to this, the proposed model also achieved higher throughput for a network with lower packet loss.

5.3 PROBLEM WITH RPL PROTOCOL FOR BURST TRAFFIC

Mainly RPL fails during the distributing routing load traffic data by using the best path with burst traffic load, however, it also misses some of the load balancing features [44]. Moreover, RPL is significantly classified as a single path rounding protocol, in this mode, all RPL nodes are capable to transmit the packets towards the targeted parent directly [40]. On the other hand, most of the networks during burst traffic cases, require selecting appropriate links which support creating new topology in terms of time slot, which is significant for the node-set to switch preferred parents constantly to fill the gap of missing load balancing features. This is mainly responsible for imitating congestion and unnecessary cost. Due to this main reason, this study has carefully proposed a congestion-aware routing metric, which is the composition of three different metrics such as OF0, rank, and the number of received packets. As the RPL routing protocol is created to handle and maintain the low power and lossy networks, due to this fact, there are still some of the most common features missing, which require more attention to fill the gap such as the self-healing approach and load balancing mechanisms [64].

5.4 Proposed BT-RPL protocol for burst traffic

This study has fixed the load balancing and congestion issues in the RPL routing protocol 1 within a case of burst traffic scenarios. Proposed work established a new

Figure 5.2: An example of the congestion avoiding technique

lexically metric called BT-RPL (Burst Traffic metric for RPL Routing Protocol). The planned metric handles a load balancing using a primary metric to compute the rank which is the hop-count metric. Also, to achieve a suitable delivery for a parent selection, a mechanism for each node to select its neighbour's node as candidate parent is proposed; whenever the candidate parent set is chosen, then straight away the second metric will start working to shift to another parent, it is all with respecting as well as considering to the number of packets which is received from neighbours to avoid the crowding point with congestion.

5.4.1 Design of BT-RPL

BT-RPL is a new mechanism for traffic load Balancing. This new mechanism is proposed to overcome the inherent problem of the RPL standard being a single-path routing protocol. RPL permits forwarding the traffic through a single parent even in the presence of multiple candidate parents which may cause several problems. These problems include higher overhead at the single parent being a parent for multiple children overhead and, also, surely consequently increasing the packet loss rate, energy depletion and load imbalance compared to other candidate parents. However, the routing metric named DBT-RPL was optimized to resolve the problem of load balancing. However, BT-RPL is a combination of the of0, Queue Utilization

(QU) and the parent count and children count (PCC).

5.4.2 Routing Metrics Used

Numerous metrics are used to measure the congestion situation at the link and node levels. Queue Utilization (QU): This metric is pointing to the neighbouring nodes which welcome another node regarding their buffer space. This objective metric is to maintain the node's buffer occupancy at the operating point of a node to show the packets' number in the i's queue out of the total queue size (see equation 1). It computes a congestion measure of random samples of an incoming packet with a probability that depends on the severity of the congestion. Based on queue utilization, every packet will be then forwarded to the best parent in terms of traffic load.

$$QU(i) = \frac{N_p Q(i)}{QS_z(i)} \quad (5.1)$$

where, $QU(i) \in [0, 1]$, $N_p Q(i)$ is the number of packets in the queue of a node i and $QS_z(i)$ is the total queue size of i .

5.4.2.1 Parent and Children Count (PCC)

(PCC) is considered the number of children and the number of parents in the selection process. Hence, if both parents have the same values of the parentNum $N_p(i)$, then the parent with the smaller number of children $N_c(i)$ will be selected as the preferred parent, otherwise, the parent with the lowest value of the PPC metric (based on parentNum) will be chosen as the preferred parent. Selecting the node with a smaller number of children as a preferred parent will enhance the load distribution among candidate parents. However, if the candidate parents have a similar number of children, I look for the parent that will minimize the interference on forwarded traffic which is the one with the minimum number of parents.

$$PPC(i) = \frac{N_c(i)}{N_p(i) + N_c(i)} \quad (5.2)$$

5.4.2.2 The Objective Function Zero (OF0)

An implementation of RPL's objective function 0 as in the following techniques:

5.4.2.3 Default Rank Calculation

Here rank of a node is calculated. The rank of the node is based on its parents rank and base rank. If the base rank is zero and the node has no parent, then the

Figure 5.3: Different Operations performed after receiving a DIO and the process of rank calculation in RPL

rank of the node is infinite. If the base rank is zero and the parent is present, then the base rank becomes equal to the parent rank. If the base rank is not zero, then depending on if the parent is present or not the increment becomes $\min(\text{hoprankinc of the parent in the DAG instance or DEFAULT_RANK_INCREMENT})$. In short, if Parent is NULL then base_rank is incremented by a default increment else it uses parent information to increment the base_rank . In the last part, if the calculated new rank is less than the base rank then the new rank becomes infinity due to wrapping around. The new calculated rank is equal to the base rank added with the increment.

5.4.2.4 Parent Selection Mechanism for Congestion Avoiding

In the wireless networking scenarios, it would be better to consider the queue utilization in the parent selection process, otherwise, the optimally balanced network may lead to worse network communication quality for some child nodes. The queue length can be quantified by Buffer Indicator. This element can be added in the parent selection process with the priority: $\text{OF0} \downarrow \text{Buffer Indicator} \downarrow \text{PCC}$. Note that the selection in the Buffer Indicator processes is not to choose the best value but to filter out candidate parent nodes according to the ranges (e.g. $-60\text{dB} \downarrow \text{Buffer Indicator} \downarrow 10\text{dB}$). This function focus on the two parents and proceeds with the best

one depending on the Objective function. in this OF, the parents are picked based on their rank as well as the OF0 value of that parent. Then a queue length as well as the number of candidate's parents and children. Therefore, this will help optimize packet delivery ratio, energy consumption, and latency, and hence, improve the overall network performance.

5.4.2.5 Introducing the Child and Parent Node Count Metric with queue utilization for load balancing

The proposed mechanism lexically combines three metrics namely the QU, of0, the number of children (childNum) and the Number of parents in the candidate parent set (parentNum) (PCC) to build a balanced topology. The comparison is done first between two candidate parents in terms of Rank, usually, the parent with the lowest Of0 value is selected as the preferred parent. However, if the difference between the two candidate parents in terms of OF0 is less than a specific threshold then, the proposed study consider the queue space. Again, if the difference between the two candidate parents in terms of queue space is more than a specific threshold then the proposed study consider the number of children and the number of parents in the selection process. Hence, if both parents have the same values of the parentNum metric, then the parent with the smaller number of children will be selected as the preferred parent, otherwise, the parent with the lowest value of the parent count metric (parentNum) will be chosen as the preferred parent. Selecting the node with a smaller number of children as a preferred parent will enhance the load distribution among candidate parents. However, if the candidate parents have a similar number of children, i look for the parent that will minimize the interference on forwarded traffic which is the one with the minimum number of parents. The details of the parent selection process are illustrated in algorithm 3.

5.5 PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The proposed work has discussed the RPL routing protocol results evaluation with packet loss ratio, power utilization, and packet delivery ratio. The performance of RPL is achieved by running the extensive simulation experiment on the Cooja simulator over the Contiki operating system. From the simulation, results show un-balanced data and congested traffic causes burst traffic, especially in higher density networks. From the results, the figure depicts the higher packets losses and power consumption that was considered in the standard RPL network where OFO is used. Proposed study also considered an effective solution that effectively optimizes the RPL performance in a burst traffic case, especially in a higher density network.

Algorithm 3 Child and Parent Node Count Metric with queue utilization for load balancing.

procedure BEST-PARENT($P1, P2, \alpha$) {P1 is the currently preferred parent}

OF0, queue utilization metric QU and P1, P2 from the parent set, α is a threshold value

if *if* $QU \geq \alpha$ *Then* **then**

Set congestion information bit along with DIO

if $P1.etx > P2.etx$ *Then* **then**

Send DIO

if $P1.etx - P2.etx < \alpha$ *Then* **then**

return P1.childNum

P2.childNum (P1:P2)

if *condition = True* **then**

else

P1. parentNum \leq P2. parentNum (P1:P2)

Return P2

while *something* $\neq 0$ **do** {Calculating alpha values}

if $P1.etx - P2.etx < \alpha$ *Then* **then**

P1. parentNum \leq P2. parentNum (P1:P2)

if $P1.etx < \alpha$ *Then* **then**

return P2. parentNum \leq P1. parentNum? (P2:P1)

Table 5.2: Simulations Parameters

Parameters	Values
Objective Function (OF)	OF0-RPL, BT-RPL
Traffic Load (PPS)	1, 20, 40, 60 pps
Density Network	30 Motes
TX Ratio	1
RX Range	100
Mote Startup Delays	1
Topologies	Random and Grid
Simulation Time	900 second

Then mainly focus to lower down the packet losses and power consumption via a good packet delivery ratio by utilizing the two main approaches such as avoiding congestion area with the help of parent nodes switches and by balancing load traffic with the help of selecting appropriate packets numbers.

5.5.1 Simulator Environment Setup

In our experiment, the standard IoT simulator is launched to be used which is named Cooja simulator. This simulator is widely used to develop IoT networks, which were selected as the best environment set according to development needs. This work have considered the SKY mote type to run our proposed scenario and to shape the network with one single source node (sink) which is set on (50,50) point, the other nodes are known as destination nodes (sender) which are allocated randomly, rest of network nodes are distributed within the range of 1000 meters of squared area. However, as shown in Table 5.2, this study applied two specific metrics to implement the RPL network consisting of the OF0-RPL and BCA-RPL. However, to compare the standard OF-RPL against the enhanced BT-RPL. The network is created based on these (10, 20, 30, 40, 50 nodes), moreover, our experiment is performed especially on burst traffic scenarios with the 30 apps. For justification, the overall experiment after providing a comparative analysis of the impact of OF0-RPL and BT-RPL via packet delivery ratio, power consumption, latency and packet loss.

5.6 SIMULATION RESULTS

Simulation results are concerning both random and grid topologies. A group of figures and tables are presented to reflect the performance evaluation comparison between OF0, ETX and BT-RPL. for different sending rates. The advantage of BT-RPL over OF0 and MRHOF is provided. simulation results presented in Figure 5.4, RX= 100% with different a send rate of 1, 20, 40, 60 PPS.

5.6.1 Packet Delivery Ratio

The packet delivery ratio (PDR) is the first performance evaluation metric used in our study, it states the ratio of the number of packets that are received at the source node successfully to the number of packets that in total sent from all other nodes. From Figure 5.4, Figure 5.5 and Figure 5.6, BT-RPL-metric has a PDR that is gradually better than OF0 and ETX ratio at light traffic load. while it shows more enhancement for regular traffic load and heavy traffic load in terms of PDR. Also, BT-RPL-metric has advanced enhancement especially in terms of burst traffic compare to OF0 and ETX where BT-RPL, OF0, and MRHOF with a percentage of 62.44%, 38.54%, and 44.84%) respectively.

Figure 5.4: The PDR Performance using OF0

On the other hand, table 5.6 show a comparison of the packet delivery ratio results with details of the traffic load setting for OF0, ETX, and BT-RPL. ETX has outperformed the performance compared to OF0 in Heavy traffic load and burst traffic load. However, BT-RPL outperforms as a high-efficiency metric in a comparison with other RPL metrics in terms of PDR with 62.44% under a traffic load within 1 packet per 1 sec.

Figure 5.5: The PDR Performance using MRHOF

5.6.2 Power Consumption

one of the main key parts of LLN performance is power consumption since these kinds of devices must operate for several years with restricted power. For the analysis of energy consumption, the Powertrace system is usually used. Also, power trace is a method provided by Contiki software to calculate the PC of the wireless networks with low power. As shown in Figure 5.7, Figure 5.8 and Figure 5.9, the BT-RPL metric has better performance over OF0 and ETX for all traffic load scenarios in terms of power consumption, with only 3.178 kb once burst traffic scenario is applied. On the other hand, in light traffic load and regular traffic load, MRHOF has an advantage in performance compared to OF0. However, OF0 has the worst energy consumption in the burst traffic load due to the highly congested routes and the higher number of retransmissions with 5.122 kb. While OF0 is in the route selection process, the ETX route does not consider since it is only about selecting the shortest route. Therefore, it is resulting in increased power consumption because that the nodes will find more packet retransmissions. However, due to the nature of loss of LLNs, link quality changes frequently and leads to frequent changes in ETX for the route. ETX will be able to reflect the link condition accurately when considering the ETX route.

Figure 5.6: The PDR Performance using BT-RP

5.6.3 Latency

Latency is defined as the overall amount of time in which the packet needs to be transferred between the source node to the destination. Package latency is the third metric performance evaluation you have used. In the network of all nodes, latency is considered as the average of all packet latencies. In Figure 5.10, Figure 5.11 and Figure 0 12they represent the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the package latency for the three metrics. It is noted that ETX and OF0 have likely a similar latency performance, also both (ETX and OF0) have a lesser amount of good performance compared to BT-RPL. Also, the performance of BT-RPL is only 2610.2 once the burst traffic scenario is applied. On the other hand, in light traffic load and regular traffic load, OF0 shows slightly better performance compared to MRHOF. However, MRHOF has the worst energy consumption in the burst traffic load due to the highly congested routes and the higher number of retransmissions with 3100.22.

In Table 5.6 Table 5.4 the latency is compared during different traffic loads between OF0, ETX, and BT-RPL. The best improvement shows the enhancement of RPL performance over burst traffic load where BT-RPL, OF0, and MRHOF has a percentage of 2610.2, 2900.2 and 3100.22) respectively. This is linked to the fact that the ETX mechanism is considering only the details of the link-level whenever

Table 5.3: Traffic Load vs. Average PDR per Second

Parameters	Values
Objective Function (OF)	OF0-RPL, BT-RPL
Traffic Load (PPS)	1, 20, 40, 60 pps
Density Network	30 Motes
TX Ratio	1
RX Range	100
Mote Startup Delays	1
Topologies	Random and Grid
Simulation Time	900 second

Table 5.4: Traffic Load vs. Average Power Consumption per Second

Setting	ETX	OF0	BT-RPL	Sec
1 packet per 60 sec	1 packet per 60 sec	1.069	1.129	60
1 packet per 40 sec	1.191	1.263	1.172	40
1 packet per 20 sec	1.297	1.338	1.254	20
1 packet per 1sec	4.167	5.122	3.178	1

the best routes are computed, also OF0 is considering only the hop-count where separates the node and the root. while BT-RPL considers the details of the queue utilization, as well as parent and children, count when computing the best routes.

5.6.4 Packet Loss

The performance of RPL network with various traffic load rate deployments. As seen, the more BT-PL traffic load used in the network, the higher packet loss is expected. Second, more BT-RPL traffic load is used in the network, in Figure 5.13, Figure 5.14 and Figure 5.15. Because the traffic level of the network in the experiments is considerably high, where BT-RPL nodes manage to make use of all the possible network capacity to enhance the throughput and cut the packet loss percentage.

Table 5.5: Traffic Load vs. Average Latency per Second

Setting	ETX	OF0	BT-RPL	Sec
1 packet per 60 sec	1 packet per 60 sec	550.34	500.44	60
1 packet per 40 sec	750.56	650.21	485.89	40
1 packet per 20 sec	1000.35	800.15	650.23	20
1 packet per 1 sec	3100.22	2900.2	2610.2	1

Figure 5.7: Power Consumption Performance using OF0

Table 5.6: Traffic Load vs. Packet Loss Per Second

Setting	ETX	OF0	BT-RPL	Sec
1packet per 60 sec	1packet per 60 sec	0.21%	0.66%	60
1 packet per 40 sec	1.94%	1.35%	0.33%	40
1 packet per 20 sec	1.87%	1.63%	0.71%	20
1 packet per 1 sec	56.16%	61.46%	37.56%	1

5.6.5 The impact of Packet Reception Ratio (PRR) on RPL under Random and Grid topology once PRR is 60% RX

After a deep analysing, this study has found out that using RPL with less PRR can provide good performance with an acceptable level of the used evaluation metrics. Therefore, after an extensive experiment, the results show that RPL performance with 60% PRR will give us a similar PDR with less power consumption and less latency in various traffic loads. The following data analysis will provide a full image of the impact of PRR over the RPL performance under various types of traffic using random and grid topology.

Figure 5.8: The Power Consumption Performance using MRHOF

5.6.5.1 PDR Comparison

Figure 5.16 shows the performance of the packet delivery ratio using random topology compared to Figure 5.17 using Grid topology. During different traffic loads between OF0, MRHOF and BT-RPL, MRHOF outperforms OF0 in terms of PDR once the rate of data is about 1pps to 40pps while OF0 and MRHOF are both starting to be a bit similar once traffic load is 60pps. On the other hand, this work observed that BT-RPL has domination PDR value over both standard RPL objective functions at low data rate and high data rate. domination and a small difference in the burst traffic load. The most significant difference was domination and a small difference for the BT-RPL performance once burst traffic is with 60PPS. BT-RPL keep the effect optimally when the random topology is used then the grid topology in this research. Moreover, there were no different values at topologies approached in this research for the data rate used. BT-RPL-metric has a PDR that is gradually better than OF0 and MRHOF ratio at burst traffic load in random topology. while it shows more enhancement for burst traffic load once grid topology is used in terms of PDR. This is indicating that BT-RPL builds a more reliable network compared to the one build once OF0 or MRHOF is used.

Figure 5.9: The Power Consumption Performance using BT-RPL

5.6.5.2 PC Comparison

The power consumption was compared during different traffic loads between OF0, ETX and BT-RPL. The graph outcome of power consumption average measurement is shown in Figure 5.18 and Figure 5.19. The BT-RPL metric has better performance over OF0 and ETX for all traffic load scenarios in terms of power consumption in random topology, with 5.166 kb once the burst traffic scenario is applied. On the other hand, in grid topology, BT-RPL has an advantage in performance compared to BT-RPL in random topology. However, MRHOF has the worst energy consumption in the burst traffic load due to the calculation of this metric which needs a more complex process than other metrics with 5.722 kb.

5.6.5.3 Latency Comparison

The measurement of the average time latency result is shown in Figure 5.20 using random topology. It is compared with Figure 5.21 using grid topology. Figure 5.12 Both figures are representing the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the package latency for the three metrics under the random and grid topology. It is noted that MRHOF and OF0 have likely a similar latency performance in random topology. Also, both (MRHOF and OF0) have a lesser amount of good performance compared to BT-RPL. Moreover, the performance of BT-RPL is only 2500.0 once

Figure 5.10: Latency Performance using OF0

the burst traffic scenario is applied in random topology. On the other hand, in grid topology, BT-RPL shows slightly a lesser amount of good performance compared to the BT-RPL scenarios applied in random topology. However, OF0 has the worst latency in the burst traffic load due to the highly congested routes and the higher number of retransmissions with 3900.50.

5.7 CONCLUSION

These studies also tackle the congestion problems and load balancing issues especially in terms of RPL routing protocol with burst traffic scenarios. Also depicted a new lexical metric method known as Burst-Traffic Metric for RPL (BT-RPL) in IoT network concerning Packet Reception Ratio. The proposed approach mainly utilizes load balancing by using the hop count metric as a main primary metric for calculating rank. From the Cooja simulator, results represent the congestion avoiding technique and load balancing technique perform better as compared to the original RPL-OF0 routing protocol. Overall, BT-RPL-metric, where BT-RPL, OF0, and MRHOF with a percentage of 62.44%, 38.54%, and 44.84%) respectively. Traffic load setting for OF0, ETX, and BT-RPL. ETX has outperformed the performance compared to OF0 in Heavy traffic load and burst traffic load. However, BT-RPL outperforms as a high-efficiency metric in a comparison with other RPL metrics

Figure 5.11: Latency Performance using MRHOF

in terms of PDR with 62.44% under a traffic load within 1 packet per 1 sec. In addition, The BT-RPL also lower down the packet loss of around 50% and power consumption, which is considered an acceptable level of the IoT networks.

Figure 5.12: Latency Performance using BT-RPL

Figure 5.13: The PACKET LOSS PERFORMANCE under various scenarios using OFO

Figure 5.14: The PACKET LOSS PERFORMANCE under various scenarios using MRHOF

Figure 5.15: The PACKET LOSS PERFORMANCE under various scenarios using BT-RPL

Figure 5.16: The Packet Delivery Ratio Values under Different Traffic Scenarios When RX=60 Using Random Topology

Figure 5.17: The Packet Delivery Ratio Values under Different Traffic Scenarios When RX=60 USING GRID TOPOLOGY

Figure 5.18: The Power Consumption Values under Different Traffic Scenarios When RX=60 Using Random Topology

Figure 5.19: The Power Consumption Values under Different Traffic Scenarios When RX=60 Using Grid Topology

Figure 5.20: The Latency Values under Different Traffic Scenarios When RX=60 Using Random Topology

Figure 5.21: The Latency Values under Different Traffic Scenarios When RX=60 Using Grid Topology

Chapter 6

Survey of Evaluations, Enhancements and Applications of IPv6 Routing Protocol for Low-power and Lossy Networks: An Attention on RPL-Objective Functions

6.1 INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) consists of a group of low-energy and remotely integrated wireless sensors that facilitate interaction through the radio access network. IoT systems are now being installed underwater, throughout the sea and underground [1]. Low-power Communications and processor units are aiming to explore with fewer resources the versatility of the integrated circuit, the key purpose of connectivity between sensor networks is data processing and transmission. Generally, each node from the sensor functions simultaneously acts as a data provider and data originator [2]. Opportunities presented by the IoT offer the potential for a vast quantity of applications to be in our world, while, only a very small quantity is available to our environment at this time, Also, most of these applications are separated into numerous domains such as, ‘Smart Environment (office, home, plant), ‘Healthcare’, ‘Transportation’ and ‘Personal and Social’ [4]. Packet forwarding is a core function in IoT that has several essential purposes and many protocols are suggesting an underlying infrastructure is usable. Routers pathways for transferring data packets from one node to another can be developed in one of 3 stages: constructive, reactive

or hybrid See section 2.2. The advent of a simplified IP-based WSN architecture made it clear that existing routing structures were never built to run well under the, even though they function well enough on wired networks. Many other vendors have discussed this problem, particularly in the home automation sector [6], by creating their customized routing solutions. Implementing those programs with the Internet, which is primarily based on standards. Routing via Low Power and Lossy Networks (ROLL) working group works with the IPv6 routing protocol for Low Power and Lossy Networks (RPL) by Standards IETF has designed the RPL routing scheme to resolve routing in low-power lossy networks regularly [79]. In reality, RPL was designed taking into account the limitations of the 6LoWPAN timeline, which become a popular choice designed for networking on IPv6 embedded networks. RPL is programmed to accept certain particular OFs, or a mixture of decision variables when selecting a path. Power required on the routes or the looseness of the relation is good instances of such OFs which will be introduced to acquire routes through RPL. However, the RPL is versatile but needs to be generalized to accommodate objectives with any features, therefore, it becomes sufficient to accomplish fairly decent efficiency in any particular scenario. Nevertheless, this versatility often raises the possibility of facing a scenario in which a complicated target feature may allow the decision-making causing a very time and energy-consuming compared to a straightforward but fixed strategy. One such mixture of strengths and potential disadvantages involved with the use of RPL makes it necessary to properly recognise this routing protocol in detail, especially after RPL is planned to turn out to be the default networking approach for 6LoWPAN networks [80]. Based on the number of existing kinds of literature related to optimizing RPL based on its OF, this study offers an incentive to solve a range of replicated solutions and offers further motivation for the creation of new OF concerning the specifications of the LLNs framework. In particular, the recent report makes it easy to eliminate common variations of routing metrics and to provide a clear insight into discrepancies in metrics and limitations. Compared with the current RPL surveys, this study is the first to concentrate on the core RPL variable, such as the OF extensively. Also, it offers a detailed description of the routing parameters used during rank computing. Our research discusses the various methods that have been reported to date for routing metric variations. This then suggests an in-depth analysis, based on data, of the research efforts made to determine the objective function, intending to extrapolate the advantages and deficiencies of the criteria of the OFs. Especially in comparison to other RPL studies, the present study addresses the technological changes that make it easier to transcend the shortcomings of the analytical function-focused mostly on the individual or composite parameters.

6.2 Motivation

Based on the number of existing literature devoted to the development of RPL focused on its OF, this review study delivers a prospect to address a range of replicated solutions and brings further encouragement to the creation of new decision variables according to the specifications of the LLNs application. In contrast, the current survey makes it so much easier to eliminate common variations of routing metrics and to provide a clear insight into discrepancies in metrics and limitations. This study is the first to concentrate on the main Routing variable, namely the Analytical Function, relative to the current RPL assessments. Thus, it offers a detailed description of the routing criteria used only for rank computing. In particular, our survey discusses the various methods reported yet for routing metric configurations. This then suggests the in-depth analysis, founded on data, of the research hard works which made to determine the OF, to extrapolate the advantages and deficiencies of the criteria of the OFs. Likened to other RPL studies, the present study addresses the technological changes that make it easier to transcend the shortcomings of the objective function-focused mostly on single or hybrid metrics.

6.3 Contribution

This journal offers a detailed and systematic analysis of research that is involved in enhancing the RPL and restrict our research to current solutions relevant to the objective function. Main aim is to focus on researching the latest methods for the collection of several routing metrics and the application which can be used in both composite and single measurements, also analyse in-depth the theoretical project suggested to address the shortcomings of analytical functions and end with some possible ways. The key contributions of this article are summarised below: To include an exhaustive overview of the routing metrics used in the RPL routing protocol and it is the feature, and illustrate the discrepancy among transport protocol and the routing limit. To provide a detailed review of the basic objective features, shortcomings, and weaknesses mentioned in the literature. To describe the various methods used for the development of performance parameters used by RPL-based objective functions. To have a detailed survey and an in-depth review of the study measures taken to resolve the suggested evaluation and improve the objective function. A descriptive and methodological study of the current RPL objective functions is presented.

6.4 Related Surveys

To present, very few studies have concentrated on different facets of RPL. Many of these observations shine a bright on the OFs of RPL and its application in different contexts to demonstrate its features and restrictions [79–81]. The main reason for this chapter is to concentrate on the OF as it is the critical part of RPL which has motivated several researchers to examine various optimizations of the RPL routing protocol. In [79], the report reviews the background of research attempts made to develop the RPL. In contrast to the steps taken by the IETF group task force on the specifications of LLNs, the formulated policies on the credibility of the RPL in the research world and how it has been studied so far. A further survey [80] reflects on the RPL provided by Contiki OS. The author discusses the Contiki OS framework and its heterogeneous group, moreover to an analysis of current literature focused on several core subjects like RPL and duplicitous connectivity. In [81], the study provides in-depth details of workable alternatives in publication involved in addressing the shortcomings of the RPL in terms of its operational activities. The study discussed the deficiencies of the RPL and explored some of the problems and drawbacks to be resolved. The research article discussed in [35] reflects on the essential elements of the RPL routing algorithm. It describes the applicable research activity related to RPL success evaluation and development. Nevertheless, the survey will not address the analysis action taken to resolve the weaknesses in the RPL. Authors in [82] assessed and examined the most important modifications of the RPL in the smartphone market. Likewise, the study in [83] provides a detailed review including its computation offloading of WSNs cantered on 6LoWPAN architecture, considering advantages and disadvantages. Conversely, the researchers did not relate current methods to RPL development. In [84], the study deals with any major attacks which could irradiate the system of 6LoWPAN and RPL protocol. The researchers concentrated mostly on the safety aspect; they did not have any attention on the centre of the RPL, particularly in the OF, although it was the basis on the ranking computational. The study [85] recommend a systematic study of the RPL and its subsequent expansion to the P2P-RPL. Recent analysis findings focused on success evaluation, problems and open-ended RPL concerns are discussed. However, the study in [86] recommends a study related to the technical observations and evaluation of the different configurations and optimisations of the Routing algorithms. While the survey sheds light on the various fields of operation of the RPL (transport, smart climate, healthcare ...), it did not include the work relevant to the OF, which has inspired us to introduce this survey. In [87] authors illustrate the various facets of RPL in terms of its application as well as the scope of use for emerging problems while proposing the enhancement of the objective function configuration. Many

surveys [80,120] address the key problems of RPL, including unbalanced transport and congestion concerns.

6.5 OVERVIEW OF INTERNET OF THINGS (IOT)

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a leading technology to vastly improve the Internet by extending that with a vast range of smart entities (WSN nodes, integrated networks, mobile phones, etc.) [9]. The Internet of Things is a concept for applying Internet access to random things by integrating the Internet into their networks. Commonly, real objects are not entirely independent from the cyber world, which allows them the capacity to be remotely operated and can establish relationships with online resources as real platforms. Indeed, the concept of the Internet of Things is founded on the notion that the current advancements in technology, telecommunications, and semiconductors that have been witnessed in preceding decades will carry on into the upcoming developments. Conversely, the Internet of Things is a storage device for certain objects in the real world, which involves several or more sensors attached to these objects, and it is also interconnected to the Internet via wireless communications internet services. These devices will use various forms of wide-area networking, like Global Mobile Communications System (GSM), Third Generation (3 G), Long-Term Evolution (LTE) and General Packet Radio Service (GPRS). Also, Sensors can provide local area interactions, including such relatively close-field connectivity (NFC), wireless fidelity (Wi-Fi) and radio frequency recognition (RFID). [9] [10] A large volume of data is always produced by the multiple sensors throughout our nearby areas [3]. The capabilities provided by IoT have the ability for a wide range of technologies to occur in our society, whereas only some relatively limited range of apps apply to our society, where the majority of apps are segregated into many fields such as 'Transportation,' 'Logistics,' 'Healthcare' 'Smart Ecosystem (office, house, plant)' and 'Economic and Social'[4]. The IoT technology provides several capabilities that allow the living creature or other entity communication more accessible to use across their communications. The goal of the IoT is to monitor and complete the measures on time. These ambiguous objectives are met with many difficulties, including the execution of specifications and the cost savings of technology, particularly if the number of items is extensively larger [10]. While a variety of initiatives were made, many of the current studies have concentrated primarily on particular elements of IoT. After all, our analysis will be a detailed IoT survey to help beginners understand the full intent of such an emerging research field.

6.6 THE IPV6 ROUTING PROTOCOL FOR LLNS (RPL)

RPL is a pragmatic distant-vector routing protocol based through IPv6, developed by the IETF group to accommodate the routing specifications of a broad range of LLN applications [32]. In specific, RPL is designed for data collection applications and includes fair support for P2MP traffic conditions, while supplying useful input for P2P patterns[32][35]. This section provides a summary of the topology underlined by the RPL and its operations to construct such an architecture (Section IV-A). Besides, a description of the uniform objective functions of the RPL (Section IV-B) is supported, whereas the functionality routing method of the RPL (Section IV-C) is incorporated. Finally, the literature provides a summary of the RPL's architectures (Section IV-D).

6.6.1 RPL Description

RPL is a remote vector protocol programmed for low-power IPv6 applications, which runs on the IEEE 802.15.4 specification with 6LoWPAN integration interface support. Working group Routing over LLNs (RoLL) implemented routing criteria for LLNs in general keeping in mind the limited capabilities in terms of resources, processing, and memory in a vision to allow large numbers of nodes to communicate in a peer-to-peer topology or overlay network topology[32]. Such protocol establishes a multihop centralized topology for nodes, in which each node will transmit information to its root node, which in response propels upward and until everything approaches the sink or gateway node. The sink node will request a unicast message to reach a particular node in its system. RPL performs data routing effectively and reliably for resource-restricted nodes, offering an operational system guaranteeing multimodal access, responsiveness, reliability, stability, and interoperability. RPL's main features originate from its powerful framework, timer usage to reduce control notifications, and target function stability.

6.6.2 RPL Hierarchy

RPL constructs a directed acyclic graph (DAG) without any adjacent nodes as the basic feature of the topology, guaranteeing that there are no loops in the structure. The sink node is starting to create the first DAG making itself the ultimate DAG core, other nodes in this DAG are starting to form their DAGs that are redirected towards the first one rendering a DAG (DODAG) directed to the endpoint. RPL incorporates many routing information to install and sustain the structure. The

DODAG Information Object (DIO) is sent from the parent node with details on the receiving node level, for example, Name, version, and DODAG-ID. It helps nodes to determine when to operate upon receipt of this post, in addition to securing important network knowledge that could lead to effective decision making. The endpoint advertising entity (DAO) was sent through a child node to its source (the DAG root or the DODAG root) and comprises relevant data that keeps reminding the root that this entity remains accessible. If necessary, the root node can preferably submit a DAO acknowledgement. DODAG information request is another type of upstream control message which is used to query a DIO from the root node, which is among the most significant and essential aspects that RPL utilizes to retain communication. Figure 1 indicates the path of the RPL routing updates.

6.6.3 RPL Upward Routes

The method of constructing the DODAG and upstream routes is regulated by the DIO [48][84]. In addition to several other routing facts, the DIOs are ranked, the relative location of the RPL node concerning the DODAG root, and the routing rule named the OF which describes how the RPL node calculates its ranking and determines its preferred chosen parent. Particularly, the development of the DODAG is undertaken by sending DODAG kernel multicast DIO communications to its nearest neighbours revealing its rank and the OF that ought to be used [84]. Nodes could also secretly dispose of the obtained DIO based on certain parameters specified in the RPL description. This situation repeats till all the nodes have set up their routes in the upward direction towards the DODAG root which can be seen in Figure 3b. Information on how RPL determines the node ranks are presented in section III.

6.6.4 RPL Downward Routes

To support the transportation facilities of P2MP and P2P, downstream paths must be identified and managed. For this function, RPL uses ICMPv6 DAOs communications. An RPL node ready to disclose itself with an open gateway from the source point of view unicasts a DAO to its chosen parent promoting its path prefix [32][90]. The transmission of the DAO obtained by the parent depends on the specific mode of service declared in the DIO messages. Towards this end, RPL defined two styles for establishing and preserving downstream routes, notably storing (table-driven) and non-storing (source routing) [32][90]. In storage mode, whenever a parent accepts a DAO as one of its descendants, it: (a) stores the declared endpoint suffix directly in its routing table together with the DAO sender address as the next hops to achieve that location; and (b) advances the delivered DAO to its own chosen parent to ensure that the identified route is extended upwards to the DODAG root[53][84].

Traditional IPv6 networking hop-by-hop can be used for data-plane functions. In the semi-storing form, the destination prefix, the displayed DAO also brings the addresses of the parent of the target. Thus, nevertheless, the parent receiving the DAO just refers it to its own chosen parent without retaining any forwarding condition before the DODAG root is eventually sent. If the DODAG roots accept the communicated DAO, it retains the information received in its route cache in the form of a child-parent relationship, which is subsequently sent by the data-plane to create a routing path for the targeted destination[32][90]. Therefore, as the root seems to connect with a specific address, it connects the originating path of that pickup point to the data packets and forwards the packet to another hop. The forwarded node that receives the packet will investigate the routing protocol header to decide that device to send a packet next to it [32]. RPL sometimes provides services for such P2P traffic conditions where a certain node connects with some other node in the cluster. Thus, when a node sends a payload to other nodes inside the DODAG, the packet is first transferred upwards at the DODAG until it meets a descendant with a known reach the destination node. Then the request is transmitted down by the descendant to the DODAG through the intermediate routers and finally to the destination host. The high-level example of these functions mentioned above is seen in Figure 3c, whilst Figure 3d displays the overall DODAG of its LLN.

6.6.5 Trickle Timer

Trickle timer [91] is also used to decrease the number of unnecessary control packets that used a continuously enhanced length. In its original location, RPL believes there should be no need for a Destination node after the communication link has been developed and hence employs the trickle timer to hold network traffic only while it relates to the server. This concept has proven to be successful in constrained devices, but it is one of the key challenges that RPL experiences mostly with the inclusion of mobile nodes. The critical variables for the trickle timer are I_{min} , $I_{doubling}$, and I_{max} . $I_{min} = 2n$ and $I_{max} = 2n + I_{doubling}$ The interval n generates I_{min} (ms) and that is the primary and minimal duration size of the trunking period as seen in equation (1). $I_{doubling}$ defines I_{max} (ms) which is the cumulative duration scale of the trickle timers as seen in equation (2). The design of the trickle timer focuses on all these variations and it is important to choose the necessary values to meet the programmed specifications. Higher delays improve energy efficiency while contributing to poor resilience, while smaller intervals increase the ability to respond to energy usage and longevity costs.

6.6.6 Objective Function

To support the overlapping criteria of multiple LLN implementations, RPL decouples routing collection and aggregation processes from key host protection like network applications and forwarding [32]. The Centre of the mechanism, therefore, focuses on the interaction of these criteria, while additional modules are configured to resolve application-specific goals such as reducing energy usage or optimizing reliability [8][16]. The term Objective Function (OF) is often used to characterize the series of procedures and regulations that control the routing availability and acceleration system in a way that satisfies the particular requirements of the target implementations. In specific terms, the OF is often used for two main purposes; first, it determines how the ranking should be extracted from one or more connectivity metrics[90] (e.g. capacity, hop count, latency, efficiency, connection efficiency, and color2), second, it describes how the rank can also be used to pick the optimal parent [8][16]. Two RPL OFs were also standardized, notably Objective Function Zero (OF0) [8] and MRHOF [90].

6.6.6.1 Minimum Rank with Hysteresis Objective Function (MRHOF)

The Minimum Rank Objective Function with Hysteresis (MRHOF) is typically referred to as the Objective Function (OF) which uses modulation when selecting the shortest path parameters. The authors in [8] addressed numerous additional statistics that support introducing MRHOF, wherein routing purpose aims to minimize standard routing metrics. At a minimum, one variable must recognize one of these links. Using MRHOF with Predicted Transmission Count (ETX) metric, though, facilitates RPL to define reliable and limited ETX channels. This Objective Function is specifically used during the identification of parents required to produce the lowest percentage of transmissions [16]. Throughout the wireless connection, the ETX parameter is required to have a propagation integer, that is necessary for seamless communication and payload identification on that access point network. This capability is critical for characterizing and distinguishing less secure routes that use wider streams for delivery from the better routes. As this parameter is useful in calculating the propagation number before the message reaches the destination and constructing a comprehensive graph of appropriate attributes, it is possible to create repetitive pathways to exploit the network isolation [8].

6.6.6.2 Objective Function Zero (OF0)

Objective Function Zero (OF0) can characterize the optimal link with minimal rank values, which allows working by abstruse metrics of the RPL DODAG Information Object (DIO) containers. OF0 is generated as default OF which allows various

RPL interoperations to be coevolutionary to this purpose, the OF norm refuses to define how relation indicators and nodes are coupled with increasing Rank and other quantities. The key goal of OF0 is to make it possible for such a node to access the DODAG Variant to generate a viable relation for a particular node collection. However, the maintenance of pathways cannot be assured on its own for such a particular metric [8].

6.6.7 RPL's Implementations

Many other vendors and open-source RPL frameworks are also introduced in the literature [92]-[103], nevertheless, as stated in [99], there's no such deployment that provides a complete set of RPL parameters has been introduced. However, RPL Open-Source Implementations and RPL Vendor Implementations are provided here. RPL Open-Source Implementations as below:

6.6.7.1 ContikiRPL

Contiki [93][8] is a robust and open-source operating system primarily developed for low-power IoT applications. Contiki represents a unique configured stimulates, with a range of IoT protocols, including 6LoWPAN and IPv6. This also requires the specification of basic protocols for the RPL specification in a code editor Contiki. Both the OF0 and the MRHOF are deployed in a library where the OF0 requires the hop-count as its transport protocol, and the MRHOF uses the ETX. In particular, all storage and – anti-storing methods of RPL are included in the current edition of ContikiRPL. In 2017, Contiki's developers unveiled a new Contiki operating system modification called Contiki-NG [100], which contains two separate RPL frameworks: RPL-classic and RPL-light. RPL-classic does have a system size of 227 KB, while RPL-light has a comparatively smaller system volume of 204 KB. The key difference between these two frameworks is that the RPL-light does not incorporate any of the functionality that appear redundant per the RPL review throughout [99], including the storage mode and the established countless examples (e.g. only one version that utilizes the MRHOF and ETX metrics has been represented). Nevertheless, all Contiki-based RPL frameworks do not have any of their security mechanisms.

6.6.7.2 TinyRPL

TinyOS will have its version of the RPL specification called TinyRPL, which is optimised for use with BLIP (Berkeley Low-Power IPv6 Stack). The new technology of TinyRPL facilitates both RPL storage and semi-storing configurations for upstream standard paths. The two regular OFs (i.e. OF0 and MRHOF) are also accepted.

After all, TinyRPL enables just one incident with several DODAGs, while it excludes any provision for RPL security software. The width of the Tiny RPL codes is narrower than that of ContikiRPL with just 113 Bytes [94].

6.6.7.3 RIOT-RPL

RIOT [102], a user interface for memory-restricted low-power wireless Internet of Things (IoT) applications, also has its implementation of an RPL specification called RIOTRPL [195]. RIOTRPL accepts the two categories of operating modes of the RPL, and only apply the OF0 with both the hop-count metric. That has a network latency of more than 105 KB; furthermore and does not provide coverage for the RPL protection modes [99].

6.6.7.4 Unstrung

Unstrung is a user-space Linux-based implementation of the RPL protocol intended for wired/Ethernet backhaul networks and gateway systems [96][97]. It can run on laptops, multipurpose IoT nodes, access points, and diagnostic devices [96]. The implementation is mostly written in C++ with a code size of 1 MB. While Unstrung supports the storing mode of RPL, it does not provide support for the non-storing mode.

6.6.7.5 SimpleRPL

Another user-space integration of RPL for Linux-based frameworks is SimpleRPL. It is implemented in python which has a code size of around 228. Concerning downstream forwarding, SimpleRPL only facilitates storage through multicast [98][99]. In contrast, only OF0 with such a hop-count parameter is provided by SimpleRPL along with the power to transform only one DODAG. Like all other applications, SimpleRPL does not have protection for the security systems of RPL since it is expected to drive in a protected environment [98]. On the other hand, RPL Vendor Implementations According to [99], numerous manufacturers, namely Samsung, Huawei, and Cisco, have introduced their implementations of RPL. The information available about some of these frameworks, though, is very limited since they are proprietary. Any of the deployed functionality has only been disclosed by Cisco in the form of an online installation guide [103]. A few other technologies, such as the RPL protected mode and the non-storage mode, were not introduced by Cisco. Cisco's RPL integration offers support for multiple OFs, including OF0, OF1 (latency), and OF1 (ETX) [103], it aims to discuss a wide variety of applications in smart homes.

6.7 RPL'S ENHANCEMENTS: OF EMERGING RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

This section analyzes the RPL OF evaluation and improvements. This work offers a detailed review of the suggested assessment and change strategies and stress their deficiencies. The optimization portion entails the introduction of independent and combined measurements. Table 6.1 outline the objective functions reviewed, including their functions, processes, and enhancement/weakness. Besides, this work presents a statistical study of the multiple appraisal and development findings of both OFs.

6.7.1 RPL based Objective Functions assessment

The paper suggests in [105] an estimation of RPL reliability based on the assessment variable. Individuals use the standard optimal solution MRHOF and the Objective Function Zero (OF0) to differentiate increasing Objective Function produces good RPL output. Multiple radio frameworks (Unit Disc Graph Model-Distance Loss, Unit Disc Graph Model- Constant Loss, Multi-Path Ray-Tracer Medium) and generalized networks are used in the simulation platform. A collection of parameters is measured to allow a distinction between the two objective functions: Packet Distribution Ratio, Monitor Traffic Latency, PC, and System ETX. As an outcome, the OF dependent on ETX (MRHOF) has superior efficiency relative to the OF dependent on a hop count (OF0) throughout all situations[106-108]. Besides, ETX dependent MRHOF depletes the performance of the algorithm, significantly in the relation of PDR, as the number of users increases. At last ETX and OF0 based MRHOF hold comparable end-to-end delays similar to 4 s. A further examination of the OFs is recommended in [109]. The investigators equate the ETX dependent MRHOF with the OF0. Those who are focused on the interoperability of the network with a probability sampling. For simulation parameters, the packet loss ratio (PLR), the delay ratio, and the CPU are chosen. As a consequence, ETX based MRHOF offers the highest network efficiency in respect of PLR and Latency while OF0 uses less PC. In comparison, the capacity of the system is not impacted either by OF0. The writers in [110] therefore have a specific idea of the assessment of the OFs. They concentrated on the use of multi-sink in the system to deduce the effect of networking efficiency. Writers use a slight deviation with a particular set of mobile sinks, 1, 5, and 10 sensor nodes. They noticed that the implementation of the multi-sink has a significant effect on the efficiency of the system. In comparison, ETX centred OF produces good performance in terms of PDR, efficiency, and power usage than Hop Count based OF does. In [111], investigators use a range of criteria

Table 6.1: Objective Functions-related assessment research.

Related Work	Number of Nodes	Topology	Environment	Results
OF0 and MRHOF [104]	(1) Receiver and (40, 80, 100 and 200) senders	Random	Static	OF0 provide lowest performances in all scenarios
OF0 and MRHOF [105]	(25, 40 and 81)	Grid and Random	Mobile and Static	MRHOF is more consistent and OF0 consume less power. Also, OF0 delivers faster convergence time
OF0 and MRHOF [106]	(20, 30, 40 and 45)	Grid and Random	Static	OF0 and MRHOF performances better with an RX = 60%
OF0 and MRHOF [107]	(30, 60, 90 and 60)	Grid and Random	Static	MRHOF performances level is best performing with heavy density like OF0 are
OF0, MRHOF _{Energy} and MRHOF _{ETX} [124]	(20, 40, 60, 80, 100, 120 and 140)	Random	Static	MRHOF performances better with low density
MRHOF _{ETX}	(11, 16, 21, 26, 31, 36, 41 and 46)	Random	Static	MRHOF _{ETX} consumes more power and it is affected by the network size.
OF0 [108]	(1, 5 and 10) Receiver, (35) Sender	Random	Static	Performances of ETX in the network is better than HC in relations of energy consumption, Throughput and PDR
HC and ETX [109]	(1 sink 25, 40, 81 senders)	Grid and Random	Static and Mobile	MRHOF performances level is not performing well like OF0 in terms of duty cycle and convergence time as well as in PC
HC, ETX, TXPFI, PFI [111]	100	Grid	Static	TXPFI is more efficient in terms of the packet drop rate and control messages collection as well as in terms of increasing convergence
OF0 and MRHOF [118]	10, 20, 30	Grid, Random manual and Linear	Mobile and Static	MRHOF performance better once static is applied, OF0 performance better once mobility is applied. All distributions have same results except linear
OF0 and MRHOF [112]	(1) receiver, (19) senders and (1) malicious node	Random	Static	APC increased once malicious is used
OF0 and MRHOF [113]	20, 30, 40	Random	Static	The PDR increased while the PC decreases

and conditions to test uniform OFs. They use fixed nodes throughout the grid allocation while the remote nodes are randomly generated. In the verification stage, in addition to the three-distribution network of 11, 20, and 50 m, three vibrational modes of 26, 50, and 82 are included. The findings demonstrate that OF0 surpasses MRHOF in terms of capability, consolidation period, and load conditions in stable grid delivery. Otherwise, either OFF behaves equally in portable-random distribution except for PCs whereby OF0 reduces energy consumption. In response to the energy-saving and conscience-adapting characteristics of the Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs), researchers in [112] research a routing measure called TXPFI that describes the estimated number of frame packets required for effective data communication. This concept can be extended to a system where a collection of malicious and non - collaborative nodes is established. The investigators tested a method that allows the use of legal and fraudulent traffic shipments. In Table 6.1, this research has presented a detailed summary and overview of the existing empirical research assessment to evaluate the Objective Functions.

A distinction can be drawn between both the word level and the complementary mix of cryptography algorithms, such as Hop Count, ETX, and packet forwarding (PFI). The results demonstrate that the use of TXPFI in RPL is far more effective than other standardized metrics in terms of reducing attackers and eliminating unstable linkages. TXPFI decreases the packet loss and greatly increases the throughput of the system according to integrated indicators. TXPFI enables a fast, interconnected network with less created control packets, making it ideal for a strained system that contains energy-efficient networking. Researchers in [118] suggest an overview of the regular objective functions, namely MRHOF and OF0. Three methods were analyzed: channel density, a form of routing protocol, and node propagation. Based on a couple of parameters, the simulation results showed that within a specific path, MRHOF offers the best output with link quality while the OF0 mobile environment delivers poor results. For different node outputs, like random, network, and manual distribution function, all objective functions have similar performance for all parameters excluding the linear location where MRHOF uses more resources and has high transport traffic power. To illustrate the relevance of rank protection in parent selection, the investigators in [113] recommend an eval-

uation of the shortcomings of the objective function. The suggested data suggests that a rank attack can preclude a specific node from participating in the DODAG construction or from reaching the destination. The outcomes of this assessment show that in comparison to OF0, MRHOF is more highly susceptible to a rank threat. In comparison, in the fraudulent case, MRHOF raises the APC by 0.01% equivalent to OF0. These findings demonstrate the significance of the weakness of rank computing when constructing a new objective function. Further evaluation of the normal objective functions is provided in [114]. The findings argue two separate hypotheses depending on the range of the transmission time and the width of the network. The findings indicate a strong effect on the output of the network of sending interval variations. The paper reflects on the heterogeneity of the parameter and its effect on the routing behaviour without concluding the best OF standards under certain conditions. Table 1 describes the various RPL-related research.

6.7.2 Recent Enhancements of the OF Based RPL

The researchers are proposing a new objective function (OF) focus on a metric: the available resources. In comparison to the conventional objective function that employs path metrics as a single parameter (e.g. MRHOF based on Projected Transmission Count) to pick the next hop to both the destination, this current OF utilizes a node variable. The findings showed that the proposed OF-Energy equalizes the amount of data between several nodes with the efficiency of propagation. In particular, this OF causes the life of the network to be improved. Nevertheless, the use of this number of metrics is also not effective since it does not recognize the consistency of the network to be connected. Similarly, Writers in [115] are suggesting a new target feature focused on energy efficiency. They are researching the effect of the latest proposals on the Network system through a real implementation of two various scenarios. Just the real-time and battery charging specifications of the WSN network are known to be tracking or detection purposes. Particularly in comparison to the OF-based ETX and OF-based hop count, OF-Energy accepts things to operate for a long time, increasing network life, while reducing link failures and pause. Utilizing energy as a single measure to upgrade the network architecture could downgrade many variables, those relevant to the link quality not mentioned in the paper. Even then, the idea is just linked to the requirement of the OFs. Another RPL analysis was carried out in the sense of smart grid connectivity operating on Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) networks [116]. The investigators are using a new Objective function based on the Hop Count routing metric to pick the chosen parents. OF0 is associated with the current objective functions that use the Predicted Transmission Count. This configuration provides improved effectiveness

and efficiency of end-to-end delay and Ra-Tio (PDR) packet distribution. However, the suggested approach is evaluated in terms of PDR and delay, which disregards other important criteria including such system existence, integration, and the number of chosen parents. The authors in [120] introduce a new objective function based on connection status called Best-Friend ETX (BF-ETX), which is proposed to improve the quality of services provided by RPL. This metric is focusing on updating the ETX in the case when the objective function will operate for nodes that are not backed up. The BF-ETX expands network performances in terms of network latency and power consumption. Nevertheless, this solution disregards important parameters for example the parent changes and convergence time that can affect the ETX updates. The authors in [117] examine the 6LoWPAN performances via a variety of RSSI and payload measurements. It comes up to the way to extrapolate the effect of the number of fragments in the MAC layer and the IPv6 packet length in the network layer. Also, the authors have used experimental results to support RPL by proposing a new A RSSI-based IPv6 routing metrics. the new routing metrics focus on enhancing the transmission quality for 6LoWPAN performance in terms of packet size, delay and throughput. Therefore, the IPv6/UDP packet reception rate will be increased. On the other hand, the authors in [119] introduce a new mechanism that fixed the problem of packet loss in PPL downward routing to achieve network reliability. They categorise the reasons for packet loss in three categories: IEEE 802.15.4 1-byte sequence number, routing inconsistency and the MAC-layer drop. Therefore, the authors express a variant of ETX which balances path length and reliability to overcome these issues. Moreover, the authors work into the idyllic choice of the best link toward the destination by improving node progression based on context awareness. These explanations let dropping the loss rates by 0.1%. But, the mechanism grows the overhead up to 27%. The proposed improvement using single metrics and composite metrics are brief in Table 11 as follow.

6.8 CONCLUSION

This review studied the objective function in detail as the main component of the Internet of Things in general and RPL routing protocol in specific. Proposed work provides a clear review for both the enhancements and the assessments that are made up to now to overcome the limitations of the objective functions. First of all this review overviewed the IoT and its characteristics. Then, will introduce the vision of the network routing protocols. Proposed work has mainly focused on the RPL routing metrics and their features. Secondly, will focus to highlight the RPL enhancements and assessments used for optimising the performance of RPL using a different objective function. Specifically, this study investigates the latest

papers that reflect the work efforts completed by the RPL community to support the objective function. This review chapter offers scientists who are interested in RPL to give additional attention to emergency actions and to examine more the Burst traffic scenarios.

Chapter 7

Conclusion and Future Directions

7.1 Conclusion

This thesis, firstly address the load balancing problem of RPL routing protocol under burst traffic using a single gateway. With simulation experiments this research empirically identified that standard RPL is not able to hold the burst traffic load. To address this issue, this research proposes a new load balancing protocol, called ETXPC-RPL, which consist of the ETX metric and the number of parent nodes for selecting the best parent. With this two-metric combination, the load is balanced in the network under burst traffic load. This work considered different traffic scenarios, the located sink, and the single gateway. This work also prevent the problem of RPL when burst traffic load occurs in the IoT network causing the network with high packet losses and stability problems. The performance of our protocol is evaluated in Cooja under various scenarios demonstrating that ETXPC-RPL outperforms the standard RPL with MRHOF and OF0 in terms of PDR and PC. Based on our results, this study concludes that the proposed algorithm is useful for RPL to hold the burst traffic scenarios. Considering more metrics and more parameters including transmission range and density network using extensive simulations, this work will be improved. Secondly, this work has tackled two major issues with RPL: the load balancing and congestion area in the RPL routing protocol under burst traffic networks. To this conclusion, this work introduced a new lexically metric called BCA-RPL. The proposed metric applies two techniques, the first technique is the load balancing technique by using the hop-count metric as a primary metric to compute the rank. The second technique is the congestion avoidance technique by switching the best parent selection to avoid the congested area. By extensive experimentation based on the Cooja simulator demonstrated that BCA-RPL worked efficiently with RPL and attained an enhancement in terms of network packet loss with 50% reduction, power consumption and PDR with an acceptable level of the

IoT network. Author also compared BCA-RPL and OFO-RPL performance, BCA-RPL performances better than the original OF0- RPL under burst traffic load with different density networks.

Thirdly, these studies also tackle the congestion problems and load balancing issues especially in terms of RPL routing protocol with burst traffic scenarios. Author also depicted a new lexical metric method known as Burst-Traffic Metric for RPL (BT-RPL) in an IoT network concerning Packet Reception Ratio. The proposed approach mainly utilizes load balancing by using the hop count metric as a main primary metric for calculating rank. From the Cooja simulator, results represent the congestion avoiding technique and load balancing technique perform better as compared to the original RPL-OF0 routing protocol. In addition, The BT-RPL also lower down the packet loss of around 50% and power consumption, which is considered an acceptable level of the IoT networks.

7.2 Future Work

Some interesting ideas and problems are still open and require further investigation. This work has briefed below some of these points.

1. We intend to use QCOF in practise on a real case research in the future.
2. RPL performance metrics with lower congestion and latency will be utilised in industrial level from small to larger size of networks specially in real-time based IoT platform
3. Studying the effects of other important system parameters which have not been considered in this research will investigate the impact of the objective function on the stability and the efficiency of RPL.
4. Study the performance of RPL with a congestion-aware duty cycle mechanism, which is probable to deliver optimizations of the end-to-end delay and packet delivery ratio performance.
5. Explore the feasibility of implementing MAC layer mechanisms, which is expected to have an impact on the performances of RPL in overall metrics.

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Appendix A

A.1 Set up an RPL network

This section aims to show the most important steps and foundations of using the Cooja simulator to set up an RPL network. This work has simulated a program working on Sky mote. However, since Contiki 2.7 has a stable version of RPL provided just download and work with this version within the virtual machine provided to you. Once downloaded, this work had to compile the SINK (Border Router) and a SENDER UDP application

A.1.1 Compile Program


```
user@instant-contiki: ~/contiki-2.7/examples/ipv6/rpl-collect
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
CC      ../../cpu/msp430/dev/uart1-putchar.c
CC      ../../core/lib/me.c
CC      ../../core/lib/me_tabs.c
CC      ../../core/dev/slip.c
CC      ../../cpu/msp430/fixxx/msp430.c
CC      ../../cpu/msp430/.flash.c
CC      ../../cpu/msp430/fixxx/clock.c
CC      ../../core/dev/leds.c
CC      ../../cpu/msp430/.leds-arch.c
CC      ../../cpu/msp430/.watchdog.c
CC      ../../cpu/msp430/.lpm.c
CC      ../../cpu/msp430/.mtarch.c
CC      ../../cpu/msp430/fixxx/rtimer-arch.c
CC      ../../core/loader/elfloader-msp430.c
CC      ../../core/loader/syntab.c
cp      ../../tools/empty-symbols.c symbols.c
cp      ../../tools/empty-symbols.h symbols.h
CC      symbols.c
AR      contiki-sky.a
CC      udp-sender.c
udp-sender.c: In function 'collect_common_send':
udp-sender.c:140:9: warning: passing argument 1 of 'rpl_get_parent_rank' from in
compatible pointer type [enabled by default]
In file included from udp-sender.c:34:0:
../../core/net/rpl/rpl.h:247:12: note: expected 'struct uip_lladdr_t *' but
argument is of type 'union rimeaddr_t *'
CC      collect-common.c
CC      ../../platform/sky/.contiki-sky-main.c
LD      udp-sender.sky
CC      udp-sink.c
LD      udp-sink.sky
rm      udp-sink.co udp-sender.co obj_sky/collect-common.o obj_sky/contiki-sky-main.o
user@instant-contiki:~/contiki-2.7/examples/ipv6/rpl-collect$
```

Figure A.1: Overview of contiki-2.7/examples/ipv6/rpl-collect folder compilation

Figure A.2: rpl-collect files